

Supplementary Information for

On the verge of domestication: early use of C4 plants in the Horn of Africa.

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Archaeological context and grinding stone analysis.

Table S1 contains a summary of archaeological context and dates associated with the grinding stones included in the analysis. Mezber and Ona Adi were excavated in units or Fields (A-E). Fields were further subdivided into areas (e.g., A1, A2, etc.) when initial excavations units were extended for any reason (Figs. S1 and S2). Excavation was by locus (plural loci), which are defined as natural or anthropogenic soil depositional units of various sizes, and as 10 cm arbitrary levels in deep loci or when minor stratigraphic variations within a locus could not be detected during excavation. Locus numbers were also assigned to walls and other features. Soil loci were further divided into pails which denote artificial or natural sedimentary sub-units within loci. Soil loci included in this paper range in volume from approximately 0.2 to 26.1 m³ with an average of 3.5 m³. The largest loci contained significant rock tumble which produced high volumes. When these loci are removed the range is 0.2 to 5.6 m³ with an average of 1.3 m³. Each soil locus was assigned to a phase based on pottery types present, stratigraphic evidence and in some cases AMS dates. When contrary information was present, for example an AMS date indicating a different but contiguous phase than ceramics/stratigraphy, this was noted (e.g., Early and Middle Pre-Aksumite). Loci with more significant phasing contradictions were not included in analyses (e.g., Early and Late Pre-Aksumite).

Fig. S1. Map of Mezber excavation fields (by S. Wood).

Fig. S2. Map of Ona Adi excavation fields (by H. Taddesse).

All diagnostic artifacts and samples recovered from loci were assigned serial numbers unique to the site. All grinding stones collected from each pail were given one serial number. If an artifact is denoted with "a" or "b", the serial number was used for two artifacts collected and bagged together from one pail. The capitalized letters "A" and "B" refer to the first and second sampled surface of the grinding stones. Most grinding stones were used bifacially and had two working surfaces, both A and B, the following which had only one grinding surface (the grinding surface is indicated below, the opposite surface is the dorsal surface): SN 615B, SN 660B, SN 3146B, SN 1125B, SN 1164B, SN 846A. In any case, both surfaces were sampled and analyzed. 12 grinding stones from Mezber (Fig. S3-S6) and 21 from Ona Adi (Fig S7-12) were analyzed (Table S1). All artifacts were made of quartzite. Morphological attribute descriptions were based on the recommendations by Wright (1) and Adams (2). Typologies were defined following modern traditional knowledge and developed through interviews and workshops with elders in the villages (see 3, 4):

- *madit* is a handstone used with the companion *maṭhan* quern in modern homes for grinding cereals;
- *wedimadqos* is a handstone used with the companion *madqos* quern in modern homes for grinding salt, spices, peppers, beans and wet-grinding of pre-ground cereals;
- *mokarai* is a hammer stone usually used to re-roughen/resharpen grinding surfaces but can also be used as a pestle.

The results of the morphological and morphometrical analysis of the grinding stones is presented in Dataset S1. The complete analysis of these grindstones has been published by Nixon-Darcus (5, 6).

Fig. S3. Analyzed grinding stones from the Initial Pre-Aksumite phase at Mezber. a) 4200/A. b) 4200/B. c) 3239a/A. d) 3239a/B. e) 3239b/A. f) 3239b/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S4. Analyzed grinding stones from the Early Pre-Aksumite phase at Mezber. a) 1104/A. b) 1104/B. c) 3220a/A. d) 3220a/B. e) 3998/A. f) 3998/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S5. Analyzed grinding stones from the Middle Pre-Aksumite phase at Mezber. a) 0615/A. b) 0615/B. c) 1832/A. d) 1832/B. e) 3146/A. f) 3146/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S6. Analyzed grinding stones from the Late Pre-Aksumite phase at Mezber. a) 0657/A. b) 0657/B. c) 0659/A. d) 0659/B. e) 0660/A. f) 0660/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S7. Analyzed grinding stones from the Late Pre-Aksumite phase at Ona Adi. a) 1164/A. b) 1664/B. c) 1167/A. d) 1167/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S8. Analyzed grinding stones from the Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition phase at Ona Adi. a) 1425. b) 1428. c) 1443/A. d) 1443/B. e) 1447/A. f) 1447/B. g) 1495. h) 1498. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S9. Analyzed grinding stones from the Early Aksumite phase at Ona Adi. a) 0846/A. b) 0846/B. c) 1027/A. d) 1027/B. e) 1125/A. f) 1125/B. g) 1018/A (Early/Middle Aksumite). h) 1018/B (Early/Middle Aksumite). Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S10. Analyzed grinding stones from the Middle Aksumite phase at Ona Adi. a) 0746. b) 0747. c) 1292/A. d) 1292/B. e) 1335/A. f) 1335/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S11. Analyzed grinding stones from the Late Aksumite phase at Ona Adi. a) 1239/A. b) 1239/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Fig. S12. Analyzed grinding stones from Post Aksumite phases at Ona Adi. a) 0066/A. b) 0066/B. c) 0077. d) 0165. e) 0469/A. f) 0469/B. Scale bar is 10 centimeters.

Table S1. Archaeological contexts and dates associated to the grinding stones included in the analysis.

Site	Year	SN	F ¹	S ²	L ³	P ⁴	Ceramic Phasing	C14 Dates	Dating Comments	GS Type
MBR	2008	1104/A	A	1	47	104	Early Pre-Aksumite	820-595 cal. BCE	Chicken tarsometatarsus AMS-date from the same locus (A1 L47 P106)	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2008	1104/B	A	1	47	104	Early Pre-Aksumite	820-595 cal. BCE	Chicken tarsometatarsus AMS-date from the same locus (A1 L47 P106)	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2008	0615/A	A	1	29	64	Middle Pre-Aksumite	731-399 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS date from the same locus (A1 L29 P65)	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2008	0615/B	A	1	29	64	Middle Pre-Aksumite	731-399 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS date from the same locus (A1 L29 P65)	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2008	0657/A	C	1	4	23	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2008	0657/B	C	1	4	23	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2008	0659/A	C	1	4	23	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Mathan (quern)
MBR	2008	0659/B	C	1	4	23	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Mathan (quern)
MBR	2008	0660/A	C	1	4	23	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Mathan (quern)
MBR	2008	0660/B	C	1	4	23	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Mathan (quern)
MBR	2011	3146/A	C	1	36	71	Middle Pre-Aksumite	728-397 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from the same context	Mokarai (hammer stone)
MBR	2011	3146/B	C	1	36	71	Middle Pre-Aksumite	728-397 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from the same context	Mokarai (hammer stone)

MBR	2012	3998/A	C	2	24	78	Early Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2012	3998/B	C	2	24	78	Early Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2012	4200/A	C	2	30	94	Initial Pre-Aksumite	1050-895 cal. BCE	Charred lentil recovered from an associated context (C2 L30 P97)	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2012	4200/B	C	2	30	94	Initial Pre-Aksumite	1050-895 cal. BCE	Charred lentil recovered from an associated context (C2 L30 P97)	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2011	3220a/A	E	1	28	43	Early Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2011	3220a/B	E	1	28	43	Early Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2011	3239a/A	E	1	32	51	Initial Pre-Aksumite	1431-1283 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from E1 L32 which is stratigraphically equivalent to E1 L33	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2011	3239a/B	E	1	32	51	Initial Pre-Aksumite	1431-1283 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from E1 L32 which is stratigraphically equivalent to E1 L33	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2011	3239b/A	E	1	32	51	Initial Pre-Aksumite	1431-1283 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from E1 L32 which is stratigraphically equivalent to E1 L33	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2011	3239b/B	E	1	32	51	Initial Pre-Aksumite	1431-1283 cal. BCE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from E1 L32 which is stratigraphically equivalent to E1 L33	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2009	1832/A	E	1	8	8	Middle Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
MBR	2009	1832/B	E	1	8	8	Middle Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)

OA	2013	0469/A	A	1	2	25	Post Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2013	0469/B	A	1	2	25	Post Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2013	0077	B	1	2	6	Post Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Wedimadqos (handstone)
OA	2013	0165	B	1	4	12	Post Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Wedimadqos (handstone)
OA	2013	0066/A	B	1	2	5	Post Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2013	0066/B	B	1	2	5	Post Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2014	1027/A	C	1	20	82	Early Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Wedimadqos (handstone)
OA	2014	1027/B	C	1	20	82	Early Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Wedimadqos (handstone)
OA	2014	1018/A	C	1	19	80	Early and Middle Aksumite	398-539 cal. CE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from same locus (C1 L19 P79) is Middle Aksumite, but ceramics indicate Early Aksumite	Madit (handstone)
OA	2014	1018/B	C	1	19	80	Early and Middle Aksumite	398-539 cal. CE	Charcoal fragment AMS-dated from same locus (C1 L19 P79) is Middle Aksumite, but ceramics indicate Early Aksumite	Madit (handstone)
OA	2014	1125/A	D	1	10	20	Early Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)

OA	2014	1125/B	D	1	10	20	Early Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2014	0746	D	1	7	10	Middle Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2014	0747	D	1	7	10	Middle Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1164/A	D	1	16	30	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1164/B	D	1	16	30	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1167/A	D	1	16	30	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Wedimadqos (handstone)
OA	2015	1167/B	D	1	16	30	Late Pre-Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Wedimadqos (handstone)
OA	2014	0846/A	D	1	10	17	Early Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2014	0846/B	D	1	10	17	Early Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1239/A	D	2	3	9	Late Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1239/B	D	2	3	9	Late Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1292/A	D	2	8	18	Middle Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)

OA	2015	1292/B	D	2	8	18	Middle Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1335/A	D	2	11	26	Middle Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1335/B	D	2	11	26	Middle Aksumite	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1425	D	2	17	42	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1428	D	2	17	42	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1498	D	2	25	56	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1443/A	D	2	19	44	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1443/B	D	2	19	44	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1447/A	D	2	20	45	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1447/B	D	2	20	45	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)
OA	2015	1495	D	2	25	56	Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite Transition	NA	Chronology determined by ceramics, stratigraphy and architecture	Madit (handstone)

¹ Field

² Square

³ Locus

⁴ Pail

Starch grain diagnosis: type descriptions, discussion, and interpretation.

The description of the starch types was done following the terminology by Reichert (7) and the International Code for Starch Nomenclature (8) when possible. 2D and 3D shape were describe using the terminology by Pagan-Jimenez (9) and Mercader et al. (10) respectively. Measurements and photographs were taken using the Olympus BX51 microscope with Olympus Stream Basic commercial software available at the laboratory of Environmental Archaeological of Universitat Pompeu Fàbra (UPF). Differential diagnosis was applied in order to propose taxonomic classifications for each starch type, following the methodology by Höhn and Neumann (11) for charcoal identification in species-rich environments (see Table S2 for a summary). Reference specimens were obtained from the modern collections of the *Culture, Archaeology and Socio-Ecological Dynamics* (CASEs) research group, available at the Laboratory of Environmental Archaeology of the Universitat Pompeu Fàbra (UPF) in Barcelona.

Table S2. Summary of the proposed taxonomic interpretations for each starch type.

Starch Typology	Taxonomical interpretation
Type 1	Andropogoneae cf. <i>Sorghum</i> sp.
Type 2	Triticeae
Type 3	Paniceae
Type 4	Eragrostideae
Type 5	Poeae
Type 6	Indeterminate USO
Type 7	Non-diagnostic
Type 8	Non-diagnostic
Type 9	Fabaceae
Type 10	Indeterminate USO
Type 11	Indeterminate USO
Type 12	Zingiberaceae USO
Type 13	Indeterminate USO
Type 14	cf. Brassicaceae USO
Type 15	Indeterminate USO
Type 16	Indeterminate USO

TYPE 1 (Fig. S13)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Prismatic in tridimensional **shape**. Mostly polygonal –but sometimes sub-rounded– in top and side views, with pentagonal and/or hexagonal faces which can appear flattened in lateral view. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** centric to slightly eccentric, mostly closed, with a visible cavity varying between Y-shaped and T-shaped. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** cross-shaped, and straight to zigzagging. **Texture** psilate to creased, sometimes showing centrifuge **fissuring**. **Lamellae** non-evident. **Pressure facets** common, sinuate-convex to straight-biangular.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $21 \pm 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 910. Range = 16 to 29.9 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

This starch type shares the general morphological parameters of reference specimens from the Andropogoneae members *Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench, *Coix lacryma-jobi* L. and *Zea mays* L. available at CASEs collections. Other Andropogoneae genera such as *Andropogon*, *Schizachyrium* and *Sorghastrum* also produce similar starch grains, though they rarely present fissuring or it is faint in comparison (see [12](#)). *Sorghum* is the only known cultivated Andropogoneae in eastern Africa, where it was most likely domesticated first – possibly in Sudan ([13](#), [14](#)). In Tigray, however, carpological evidence of *Sorghum bicolor* has been only found after the 4th century CE, in Late Aksumite contexts at Kidane Mehret and the Tomb of the Brick Arches at Aksum ([15](#)). Evidence of Job's tears has been found in the Roman port of Berenike in southern Egypt ([16](#)), along with Aksumite coins dating from 270/290-330 CE ([17](#)). As so, *Coix lacryma-jobi* cannot be fully discounted even though it has never been documented in any Pre-Aksumite or Aksumite site so far. Noteworthy, previous morphometric studies have shown *Coix lacryma-jobi* to be slightly smaller than the presented type ([18–20](#)) while the size of starch grains from *Sorghum bicolor* completely overlap ([10](#), [21](#), [22](#)). Maize is known to have been introduced to Africa after the 15th century CE ([23](#)). Furthermore, maize starch grains are commonly spherical to irregularly shaped, with a mean maximum length of $14 \pm 2.7 \mu\text{m}$ ([24](#), [25](#)). TYPE 1 also shows similarities with starch granules from *Prosopis* sp. ([26](#)) and *Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) Morrone ([21](#)). However, the genus *Prosopis* sp. is not native to Ethiopia ([27](#)), and no carpological evidence of it has been recorded so far in association with Pre-Aksumite or Aksumite contexts. Regarding *Pennisetum glaucum*, it rarely produces starch grains larger than 15 μm ([7](#), [21](#)) –see discussion of TYPE 3 below for separation between Paniceae and Andropogoneae. Since TYPE 1 is present in our assemblage since 1600 BCE, we have considered it to be diagnostic of Andropogoneae cf. *Sorghum* sp.

Fig. S13. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 1, Andropogoneae (Panicoideae).

TYPE 2 (Fig. S14)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Lenticular biconvex in tridimensional **shape**. In top view, it is spherical to subrounded, and elliptical in lateral view. **Birefringence** variable, but always stronger in lateral view. **Hilum** centric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** X-shaped, and straight. **Texture** psilate to creased, often with small craters on surface, and no **fissuring**. **Lamellae** sometimes present but faint, forming symmetric circles with a sinuate outline. **Pressure facets** mostly absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $25.7 \pm 4.9 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 364. Range = 15.2 to 41.6 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

The morphological features of this starch type match those of reference starch samples from various members of the Pooideae subfamily from the CASEs reference collection at UPF, namely species of *Aegilops tauschii* Coss., *A. speltoides* Tausch, *Hordeum vulgare* L., *Secale cereale* L., *Triticum aestivum* L., and *T. diccocon* Schrank ex Schübl –all of which pertain to the Triticeae tribe. Previous descriptions of Triticeae starch by Reichert (7), Piperno et al. (28), Yang and Perry (19) or Cagnato et al. (29) also match the described archaeological type. According to these authors, TYPE 2 also appears in other Pooideae members such as *Bromus* (19, 28), *Elymus* (19) or *Piptathereum* spp. (28) – all of them recorded in modern Ethiopia (30). However, these commonly produce flattened, angular-to-irregular (*Bromus* spp.) grains, which can show a compound grain structure (*Piptathereum* spp.) or feature noticeably smaller starch grains than Triticeae (*Bromus*, *Elymus* spp.) (7, 19, 28, 29). Furthermore, none of these species has been documented at either Mezber or Ona Adi carpological assemblages (31, 32), or any other of the studied Pre-Aksumite or Aksumite archaeobotanical assemblages in the region (15, 33–35). In fact, *Aegilops* and *Secale* sp. seeds have not been recorded at any site either, but the mean size of TYPE 2 falls within range of both genera so we cannot discount them. As so, we have chosen to consider TYPE 2 as diagnostic of Triticeae.

Fig. S14. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 2, Triticeae (Pooideae).

TYPE 3 (Fig. S15)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Prismatic in tridimensional **shape**. Top and side views are subrounded to polygonal, generally with pentagonal and/or hexagonal faces. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** centric, generally closed, sometimes with a visible cavity varying between linear A, Y-shaped, and stellate. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** cross-shaped, and straight to slightly curved. **Texture** psilate, with no **fissuring**. **Lamellae** non-evident. **Pressure facets** often present, sinuate-convex.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $12.2 \pm 2.3 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 311. Range = 7.5 to 15.9 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Numerous Paniceae reference specimens from the CASEs collection show matching morphological characters with TYPE 3, including *Digitaria ciliaris* (Retz.) Koeler, *Echinochloa colona* (L.) Link, *E. frumentacea* Link, *E. crus-galli* (L.) P.Beauv., *Panicum miliaceum* L., *P. sumatrense* Roth ex Roem. & Schult., *Pennisetum glaucum* (L.) R.Br., *Setaria italica* (L.) P.Beauv., *S. pumila* (Poir.) Roem. & Schult., *S. verticillata* (L.) P.Beauv, and *Urochloa ramosa* (L.) T.Q.Nguyen. Previous studies on Paniceae starch morphometrics have shown generally smaller average size than the present sample (18, 19, 21, 36, 37), though most still overlap in range. In this sense, a recent study by Ma et al. (38) showed that the mean size of millet starch grains could increase up to 1.2 times after grinding, which could explain the slightly longer length of the archaeological granules of the studied assemblages considering that they all were recovered from grindstones. Similar morphologies were identified within other Panicoideae members present in the study region, for example *Sorghum bicolor* of the Andropogoneae tribe. However, sorghum starch granules –as well as those from other Andropogoneae members such as *Coix lacryma-jobi*– are noticeably larger, reaching up to 30 μm , and show more severe fissuring (10, 36, 37). Other known potential species with similar starch characteristics in the area are *Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter and *Eleusine coracana* Gaertn., both pertaining to the Chloridoideae-Eragrostideae subclade. In this case, both species feature compound starch grains formed by notably smaller granules (very rarely larger than 10 μm), and sharper faceting. Similar descriptions have been provided by authors such as Reichert (7) and Ahituv and Henry (22). These criteria have also been used by Lucarini and Radini (39) to separate Eragrostideae and Paniceae starch in Mid-Holocene contexts of the Farafra Oasis in Egypt. In their paper, they were able to further separate TYPE 3 into types associated to the Digitariineae, Cenchrineae and Setariineae subtribes, proposing identifications to the genus/species level based on the carpological record of the site. Even though carpological analysis at Mezber and Ona Adi have also shown presence of seeds from different Paniceae subtribes (31, 32), we have chosen to keep the taxonomic classification of TYPE 3 at the tribe level.

Fig. S15. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 3, Paniceae (Panicoidae).

TYPE 4 (Fig. S16)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure compound. Compound grains prismatic to parabolic prismatic in **shape**. Individual grains polygonal, both regular and irregular, showing 4- to 6-sided faces. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** centric, closed, cavity absent. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** cross-shaped, and straight to slightly curved. **Texture** psilate, with no **fissuring**. **Lamellae** non-evident. **Pressure facets** present, mostly straight-biangular.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $4.8 \pm 0.7 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 10 compound grains, with 103 observable component granules. Range = 3.2 to 6.8 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

The archaeological starch TYPE 4 largely matches the characteristics of reference granules from *Eragrostis tef* (Zucc.) Trotter. It is noteworthy that wild species of *Eragrostis* also show similar morphometrical parameters—for example, *E. sarmentosa* Nees (22) or *E. pilosa* (L.) P.Beauv. (40). Morphometrical features show that TYPE 4 is similar to *E. tef* reference starches in size (Length = $4.3 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{m}$, n = 50. Range = 3.1 to 6.3 μm). Previous studies record similar morphometrical ranges for *E. tef* (7, 22). Other genera with similar starch morphology that were used during Pre-Aksumite and/or Aksumite periods include *Avena* (Avenae, Pooideae), *Eleusine* (Eragrostideae, Chloridoideae), and *Lolium* (Poeae, Pooideae), as well as several genera of the Amaranthaceae family (e.g., *Beta*, *Chenopodium*). Whereas Pooideae members (*Avena*, *Lolium* spp.) do not produce polyhedral compound grains, Amaranthaceae show noticeably smaller component grains (7, 29). Finally, *Eleusine* starch demonstrates very similar morphological traits, although individual grains are more common. Published morphometrical data on *Eleusine coracana* Gaertn. (19) show its granules to be slightly bigger than the presented type (Length = $6.8 \pm 1.6 \mu\text{m}$, n = 100-150. Range = 3.3 to 11.8 μm), but still encompassing the range of TYPE 4. As for its wild relative, Mercader et al. (10) found *Eleusine africana* Kenn.-O'Byrne granules to be of similar length, in this case reaching up to 12.3 μm . Whereas macrobotanical evidence of *Eragrostis tef* has been documented at Mezber during the Late Pre-Aksumite phase (ca. 400 BCE – 1 CE) (31), *Eleusine coracana* has been only tentatively identified during the Late Aksumite phase (ca. 500-700 CE) at Ona Adi (32). Yet, TYPE 4 has been found in grindstones associated to the Initial Pre-Aksumite occupation at Mezber (ca. 1600-900 BCE), hence the presence of wild relatives of t'ef and finger millet cannot be discounted. We have decided to consider TYPE 4 as diagnostic of the Eragrostideae tribe.

Fig. S16. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 4, Eragrostideae (Chloridoideae).

TYPE 5 (Fig. S17)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure compound. Compound grains globular to cylindroid elliptical in **shape**. Individual grains polygonal, mostly irregular, with 5- to 6-sided faces. **Birefringence** weak. **Hilum** centric, closed, cavity absent. **Extinction cross** visible, but faint. **Arms** non-determinable. **Texture** psilate, with no **fissuring**. **Lamellae** non-evident. **Pressure facets** present, straight-biangular.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $3.1 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 4 compound grains, with 72 observable component granules. Range = 1.0 to $3.7 \mu\text{m}$).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

TYPE 5 matches the morphological character from reference starch grains from various members of the Poeae tribe, including *Avena*, *Calamagrostis*, *Festuca*, *Lolium*, *Phalaris* and *Poa* spp. available in CASEs reference collection. Other economically important taxa present in northern highlands that produce similar compound starch grains include *Rumex* spp. (Polygonaceae), which show generally bigger component granules, reaching up to 7-12 μm depending on the species (7, 19, 22, 29); as well as some members of the Amaranthaceae family, including *Beta vulgaris* L. or *Chenopodium album* L. (29), although they generally show a much stronger birefringence under polarized light. Overall, the differentiation between Amaranthaceae/Chenopoideae and Poeae starch is challenging. In this sense, the carpological record shows the use of Amaranthaceae in Tigrai to date back to the Pre-Aksumite period, as seeds of Chenopoideae/Amaranthaceae have been identified at Pre-Aksumite contexts from the Kidane Mehret site at Aksum (15), but also at Mezber, where 6 seeds of *Chenopodium*/*Amaranthus* have been recorded (31). Similarly, carpological analyses at Ona Adi record the presence of *Chenopodium album* since the Pre-Aksumite to Aksumite transition (32). By contrast, seeds of Poeae members such as *Lolium* spp. have been identified at both Mezber and Ona Adi. Morphometrics from reference *Lolium* species also overlap with the archaeological type (*L. perenne* L.: $L = 2.2 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{m}$, n = 50; *L. temulentum* L.: $L = 2.0 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, n = 50). Still, Poeae is a complex and vast tribe and the available morphometrical data is still very limited. As such, we have chosen to consider TYPE 5 as indicative of the Poeae tribe.

Fig. S17. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 5, Poaeae (Pooideae).

TYPE 6 (Fig. S18)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Conoid guttiform in tridimensional **shape**. Obovate-obtuse elongated in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** weak. **Hilum** eccentric to hyper-eccentric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** cross-shaped, and straight to slightly curved. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** non-visible. **Pressure facets** sinuous-convex.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $17.2 \pm 2.4 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 40. Range = 13.4 to 23.2 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

TYPE 6 shows some of the typical features of USO starch grains. However, the available reference collection did not include any that showed enough morphologic and morphometric characteristics to be considered a modern analogue of TYPE 6. Regarding published starch data, the closest matches are within the genus *Dioscorea* spp. (10). However, in most *Dioscorea* spp., the hilum is located at the thinner end of the conoid granules, whereas in the archaeological type it is always in the base of the cone. Consequently, we have decided to classify TYPE 6 as diagnostic of Indeterminate USO.

Fig. S18. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 6, Indeterminate USO.

TYPE 7 (Fig. S19)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Globular in tridimensional **shape**. Orbicular in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** eccentric, closed, sometimes showing a Y-shaped cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** X-shaped, and curved. **Texture** psilate, with **no fissuring**. **Lamellae** non-visible. **Pressure facets** mostly absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $17.2 \pm 2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 71. Range = 13.2 to 22.9 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

There are several genera that produce starch grains with morphological features similar to TYPE 7. These include *Typha* spp., as well as various taxa within the Cyperaceae and Polygonaceae families ([10](#), [22](#), [29](#), [41](#)). Still, the potential candidates within these taxa usually produce smaller granules. Since TYPE 7 is known to be produced in underground storage organs (USO) and seeds of different species, we have considered it to be non-diagnostic.

Fig. S19. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 7, non-diagnostic.

TYPE 8 (Fig. S20)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Globular in tridimensional **shape**. Orbicular in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** variable. **Hilum** centric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** mostly visible. **Arms** cross-shaped, and straight. **Texture** psilate, with **no fissuring**. **Lamellae** non-visible. **Pressure facets** mostly absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $8.9 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 61. Range = 7.1 to 10.2 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

TYPE 8 shows morphological features that largely coincide with the smaller starch granules of some members of the Pooideae subfamily that produce bimodal starch such *Triticum* and *Hordeum* spp. According to published literature, however, similar granules are produced by several other eastern African plants from a wide range of taxonomical clades, including Poales and Fabales amongst others ([10](#)). As such, we have considered it to be non-diagnostic.

Fig. S20. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 8, non-diagnostic.

TYPE 9 (Fig. S21)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Cylindroid elliptical to cylindroid irregular in tridimensional **shape**. Elliptical to reniform bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** centric, closed, showing a mesial longitudinal cleft fissure. **Extinction cross** visible, commonly cryptic. **Arms** X-shaped, and straight. **Texture** psilate to creased, with no **fissuring**. **Lamellae** sometimes present, forming symmetric circles, but mostly faint. **Pressure facets** absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $21.2 \pm 5.3 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 61. Range = 14.3 to 33.1 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

This starch type resembles the morphology of starch grains from reference materials from Fabaceae members such as *Cicer arietinum* L., *Lathyrus sativus* L., *Lens culinaris* Medik., *Pisum sativum* L., *Vicia sativa* L. and *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp. Similar to the starch produced by these species, TYPE 9 comprises a broad morphospace which includes starch granules of different sizes that share core morphological features –such as their cylindric shape and a cryptic extinction cross. In this sense, the presence of a mesial longitudinal cleft fissure is common to most cultivated legumes, as well as some of their wild relatives. In fact, it has been considered to be a diagnostic characteristic for the group ([22](#), [41](#)). Regarding the carpological evidence, the available studies suggest that lentil (*Lens culinaris*) was the only legume present during the Pre-Aksumite period, and that other species such as chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) or Abyssinian pea (*Pisum abyssinicum*) were introduced during Aksumite times ([15](#)). Whereas carpological analysis at Pre-Aksumite Mezber confirms this hypothesis ([31](#)), the initial study carried out at Ona Adi has shown no evidence of any type of legume ([32](#)). Since TYPE 9 could represent one or more of the aforementioned Fabaceae species, we have chosen to keep its taxonomical interpretation at family level at both sites.

Fig. S21. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 9, Fabaceae.

TYPE 10 (Fig. S22)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Parabolic Prism in tridimensional **shape**. Oval-Irregular Expanded in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** eccentric, closed, with linear A to lineal G cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** X-shaped, curved to wavy. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** non-evident. **Pressure facets** sometimes present, but rare, sinuous-convex.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $20.4 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 37. Range = 16.6 to 27.3 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

No modern starch analogue was found in available reference materials. TYPE 10 shows morphological features that are diagnostic of USO, namely its eccentric hilum and extinction cross with curved to wavy arms ([10](#), [22](#), [29](#), [41](#)). In the published literature, the closest match is *Dioscorea schimperiana* ([10](#)), though the reference specimens show clearly visible concentric ring-shaped lamellae. Due to the state of preservation of the archaeological type, the presence of lamellae is unclear and hence we have considered TYPE 10 to be indicative of Indeterminate USO.

Fig. S22. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 10, Indeterminate USO.

TYPE 11 (Fig. S23)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Lobate-Shell in tridimensional **shape**. Oval-Triple Irregular in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** eccentric, closed, with T-shaped cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** X-shaped, curved to slightly wavy. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** non-evident. **Pressure facets** absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $21.8 \pm 2.6 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 25. Range = 17.6 to 26.7 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

No modern starch analogue was found amongst available reference materials or published literature. Still, TYPE 11 shows morphological features that are diagnostic of USO (see [10](#), [22](#), [29](#), [41](#)). Consequently, we have classified TYPE 11 as Indeterminate USO.

Fig. S23. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 11, Indeterminate USO.

TYPE 12 (Fig. S24)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Pyriform in tridimensional **shape**. Obovate-compressed to obovate-triangular in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** hyper-eccentric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** X-shaped, curved. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** non-visible. **Pressure facets** absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $27 \pm 6.3 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 10. Range = 20.1 to 39.1 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

The morphological features of TYPE 12 match those of the starch grains from reference materials from species such as *Zingiber officinale* Roscoe and *Curcuma longa* L., both members of the Zingiberaceae. However, *C. longa* often shows a more irregular cylindroid shape. Still, Reichert ([7](#)) notes that both genera, along with *Hedychium* spp., show very similar histological characteristics and hence visual differentiation can be challenging. Indeed, previous publications have preferred to stay at the family level ([42](#), [43](#)). To date, no archaeobotanical evidence of Zingiberaceae has been found in Pre-Aksumite or Aksumite contexts. However, this is not unusual as the most consumed part of the plants is the rhizome, which is rarely preserved. As such, we have considered TYPE 12 as diagnostic of the Zingiberaceae family.

Fig. S24. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 12, Zingiberaceae.

TYPE 13 (Fig. S25)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Cylindroid elliptical to cylindroid oval in tridimensional **shape**. Elliptical in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** eccentric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** X-shaped, and wavy. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** sometimes present, forming eccentric circles, but faint. **Pressure facets** absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $22.9 \pm 2.9\mu\text{m}$ (n = 11. Range = 19.5 to 27.8 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

No modern starch analogue was found amongst available reference materials. Still, TYPE 13 shows morphological features that are diagnostic of USO. According to published starch morphological data, potential candidates would include *Plectranthus edulis* (Vatke) Agnew and *Dioscorea* spp. (44) –both indigenous to Ethiopia– as well as members of the genus *Brassica* spp. (29) – Brassicaceae seeds have been found at both Pre-Aksumite and Aksumite occupations around Aksum (15), as well as at Ona Adi (32). Similar starch grains are also produced by members of the Solanaceae family (45) –seeds of Solanaceae have also been found in the Aksum sites associated with both Pre-Aksumite and Aksumite occupations (15). Overall, we decided to consider TYPE 13 as diagnostic of Indeterminate USO.

Fig. S25. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 13, Indeterminate USO.

TYPE 14 (Fig. S26)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Cylindroid oval in tridimensional **shape**. Obovate to ovate obtuse-elongated in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** eccentric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** cross-shaped, and wavy. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** sometimes present, forming eccentric circles. **Pressure facets** absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $49.6 \pm 9.2 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 5. Range = 40.1 to 62.1 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

The morphological features of TYPE 14 agree with those typically diagnostic of USOs (see above). Amongst the indigenous Ethiopian geophytes, only *Ensete ventricosum* (Welw.) Cheesman and *Plectranthus edulis* produces starch granules of similar size (44), though the shape greatly varies in both cases. More consistent producers of TYPE 14 include members of the Brassicaceae family such as *Brassica rapa* (29), even though some of its members such as *B. nigra* (L.) W.D.J.Koch or *B. tournefortii* Gouan have been found to produce few to no starch grains (22). Seeds of Brassicaceae have been documented by Boardman (15) in the Aksum area during Pre-Aksumite and Aksumite times. Similarly, carpological remains of *Brassica* sp. have been recorded at Ona Nagast (46) and Ona Adi (32). Overall, we decided to consider TYPE 14 as diagnostic of cf. Brassicaceae.

Fig. S26. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 14, cf. Brassicaceae USO.

TYPE 15 (Fig. S27)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Conoid fusiform in tridimensional **shape**. Oval-crescent in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** hyper-eccentric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** X-shaped, and straight to curved. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** present, but faint, forming concentric rings. **Pressure facets** absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = $42.7 \pm 4 \mu\text{m}$ (n = 3. Range = 39.3 to 47.2 μm).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Even though no modern starch analogue was found amongst available reference materials, TYPE 15 features the morphological characteristics typical in USOs mentioned above. Amongst published materials, the only local species known to produce starch grains with similar features is *Plectranthus edulis* and possibly *Ensete ventricosum* (44). However, the available images do not allow for a secure identification without comparison against reference specimens. Further, there are other taxa within the Liliaceae family showing a similar morphology (e.g. *Lilium* sp.). As such, we have decided to classify TYPE 15 as Indeterminate USO.

Fig. S27. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 15, Indeterminate USO.

TYPE 16 (Fig. S28)

- **Description of starch type:**

Grain structure simple. Reniform in tridimensional **shape**. Oval-Kidney in bidimensional shape. **Birefringence** strong. **Hilum** hyper-eccentric, closed, with no visible cavity. **Extinction cross** visible. **Arms** cross-shaped, and wavy. **Texture** psilate. **Lamellae** non-visible. **Pressure facets** absent.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length = 34.3 μm (n = 1).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

No modern starch analogue was found amongst available reference materials. Still, TYPE 16 shows morphological features that largely agree with those of USO starch grains (see [10](#), [22](#), [29](#), [41](#)). As such, we have considered it as diagnostic of Indeterminate USO.

Fig. S28. Archaeological starch grains identified as Type 16, Indeterminate USO.

Phytolith diagnosis: type descriptions, discussion, and interpretation.

Phytolith morphotypes were named according to the International Code for Phytolith Nomenclature 2.0 (ICPN 2.0) (47). Morphotypes not included in the Supplementary Information of the ICPN 2.0 were named following the principles for naming phytolith morphotypes listed in the main ICPN 2.0 publication (47). The description of the phytolith morphotypes also followed the terminology of the ICPN 2.0, and its glossary of descriptive terms when possible. When ICPN 2.0 lacked specific terms, names used in previous specialized publications were prioritized (for example 48–50 for the shape of projections amongst ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE). Microscopic photographs were taken using an Euromex iScope microscope at 400x magnification and an Euromex scientific camera sCMEX-6 available at the laboratory of Environmental Archaeological of Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF). Anatomic and taxonomic attributions were proposed by differential diagnosis, following the example of the methodology proposed by Höhn and Neumann (11) for charcoal identification in species-rich environments (see Table S3 for a summary).

Table S3. Summary of the proposed anatomic and taxonomic interpretations for each phytolith morphotype

Morphotype	Anatomical attribution	Taxonomical interpretation
ELONGATE ENTIRE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae/Cyperaceae
ELONGATE DENTATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
ELONGATE DENDRITIC	Inflorescence	Poaceae
ELONGATE SINUATE REGULAR	Leaf	Poaceae/Cyperaceae
ELONGATE SINUATE IRREGULAR	Leaf	Poaceae/Cyperaceae
ELONGATE SINUATE CASTELLATE	Leaf	Poaceae/Cyperaceae
ELONGATE SINUATE CLAVATE	Leaf	Poaceae/Cyperaceae
ELONGATE SINUATE COLUMNAR	Leaf	Poaceae/Cyperaceae
ELONGATE SINUATE WAVY	Inflorescence	Andropogoneae
ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE Λ -shaped	Inflorescence	<i>Setaria</i> type
ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE β -shaped	Inflorescence	<i>Echinochloa</i> type
ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE Ω -I	Inflorescence	Paniceae
ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE Ω -II/III	Inflorescence	<i>Setaria</i> type
ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE η -shaped	Inflorescence	<i>Panicum/Pennisetum</i> type
BILOBATE VERY LARGE/VERY LONG SHANK	Non-diagnostic	cf. Aristidoideae
BILOBATE LARGE/LONG SHANK	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
BILOBATE MEDIUM/LONG SHANK	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
BILOBATE MEDIUM/SHORT SHANK	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
BILOBATE MEDIUM/CONSTRICTED SHANK	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
BILOBATE SMALL/CONSTRICTED SHANK	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
BILOBATE PLATEAUED	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
POLYLOBATE NODULAR	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
POLYLOBATE TRILOBATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
POLYLOBATE MULTILOBATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
CROSS TABULAR	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae

CROSS TRAPEZIFORM	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
CROSS CARINATE	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae
CROSS TRIANGLE	Non-diagnostic	Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
SADDLE TABULAR SYMMETRICAL	Non-diagnostic	Chloridoideae
SADDLE TABULAR LONG	Non-diagnostic	Chloridoideae
SADDLE TABULAR SHORT	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM BILOBATED	Non-diagnostic	cf. Panicoideae/Chloridoideae
SADDLE COLLAPSED	Non-diagnostic	cf. Chloridoideae
RONDEL TABULAR PSILATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
RONDEL TABULAR CORNICULATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM PSILATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM CORNICULATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
RONDEL CARINATE	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
RONDEL C3	Non-diagnostic	Pooideae
TRAPEZOID	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae
CRENATE SINUATE	Non-diagnostic	Pooideae
CRENATE CRENATE	Non-diagnostic	Pooideae
PAPILLATE	Inflorescence	Poaceae
ACUTE BULBOSUS	Non-diagnostic	Poaceae/Cyperaceae
ACICULAR FUSIFORM	Non-diagnostic	Non-diagnostic
SPHEROID PSILATE	Non-diagnostic	Non-diagnostic
SPHEROID ECHINATE ARECACEAE	Non-diagnostic	Arecaceae
SPHEROID ECHINATE ZINGIBERALES	Non-diagnostic	Zingiberales
SPHEROID ORNATE Plicate	Non-diagnostic	Zingiberales
SPHEROID ORNATE VERRUCATE	Non-diagnostic	cf. Zingiberales
SPHEROID ORNATE NODULATE	Bark/Wood	Dicotyledonous
COMMELINACEAE CONICAL CYANOTIS	Seed	<i>Cyanotis</i> sp.
COMMELINACEAE CONICAL COMMELINA	Seed	<i>Commelina</i> sp.
COMMELINACEAE PRISMATIC ANISOPOLAR	Seed	Commelinaceae
CYPERACEAE CONICAL PSILATE	Culm/Leaf	Cyperaceae
CYPERACEAE CONICAL GRANULATE	Fruit	Cyperaceae
STOMATE	Leaf	Poaceae
MESOPHYLL	Leaf	Dicotyledonous
TREACHERY	Culm/Leaf	Non-diagnostic
TABULAR POLYGONAL	Non-diagnostic	Non-diagnostic
TABULAR AMOEBOID	Non-diagnostic	Dicotyledonous
SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID	Non-diagnostic	Dicotyledonous
BLOCKY	Non-diagnostic	Non-diagnostic
BULLIFORM FLABELLATE	Leaf	Poaceae/Cyperaceae

ELONGATE ENTIRE (ELO_ENT)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 8).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 8).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Maximum length ranges from 15 to 150 μm . Length to width (L:W) ratio greater or equal to 2.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes or variants were differentiated during analyses. ELONGATE ENTIRE was more frequently found alone (Fig. S29a-b) though articulated silica skeletons are also common (Fig. S29c-d).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

L:W ratio ≥ 2 was used to differentiate ELONGATE ENTIRE from BLOCKY (L:W ratio < 2), following ICPN 2.0. Criteria from Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 30) were also used to differentiate ELONGATE ENTIRE from long TRAPEZOID phytoliths. Transitional forms between ELONGATE ENTIRE and other non-smooth elongate morphotypes were always considered to be the latter.

ELONGATE ENTIRE results from cell silicification within several plant tissues, most commonly in the epidermis long cells. It is the dominant morphotype in C3 and C4 Poaceae leaves and culms, and it is also present in cereal inflorescences. Additionally, it has been found in lycophytes, conifers, non-grass herbaceous monocotyledons and eudicotyledons, hence representing one of the most frequent morphotypes among plant taxa ([47](#)). While some phytolith studies in Africa have considered ELONGATE ENTIRE as non-diagnostic ([51–56](#)), others have considered it as indicative of Poaceae ([57–61](#)), or Poaceae and Cyperaceae ([62–65](#)). In this research, we have considered it to be indicative of Poaceae/Cyperaceae as they are the highest producers of this morphotype and represent the main input of ELONGATE ENTIRE into archaeological sites where agriculture is practiced.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Elongate psilate ([52](#), [53](#), [58](#), [59](#), [61](#), [63](#), [64](#), [66](#)), Elongate smooth ([51](#), [54](#), [57](#), [60](#), [62](#)), Elongate triangular psilate ([53](#), [54](#)), Elongates without decorated margins ([55](#)), Tabular ([56](#)), Articulated elongate ([65](#)).

Fig. S29. ELONGATE ENTIRE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-b) Single celled ELONGATE ENTIRE. c-d) Articulated ELONGATE ENTIRE. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

ELONGATE DENTATE (ELO_DET)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data Supplementary Data File 1: 12).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 12)

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Maximum length ranges from 15 to 150 µm. L:W ratio greater or equal to 2.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were differentiated during analyses. ELONGATE DENTATE was mostly found alone (Fig. S30a-c). Articulated silica skeletons were also present (Fig. S30d).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Transitional forms with other elongate phytoliths were documented. ELONGATE ENTIRE/DENTATE and ELONGATE SINUATE/DENTATE were classified as ELONGATE DENTATE. ELONGATE DENTATE/DENDRITIC were considered to be ELONGATE DENDRITIC.

Poaceae are the primary producers of ELONGATE DENTATE. This morphotype is recurrent in Poaceae leaves and inflorescences, forming a continuum with ELONGATE DENDRITIC in grass inflorescence. It has also been identified in the leaves of certain conifers, ferns, and non-grass monocotyledons although in fewer numbers ([47](#)). Although sometimes considered to be non-diagnostic in palaeoecological studies ([52](#)), ELONGATE DENTATE is generally associated with the Poaceae ([57](#), [59](#)) or Poaceae and Cyperaceae families ([51](#), [62](#), [63](#)). However, a recent review of Cyperaceae phytoliths from African sedges did not identify ELONGATE DENTATE ([65](#)). Additionally, some authors have considered it as diagnostic of grass inflorescence ([67](#), [68](#)) as ELONGATE DENTATE is common in the glumes of several grasses, especially in domesticated cereals such as wheat, barley, oat, and sorghum. This interpretation holds even more value when working in archaeological contexts from the Holocene ([61](#)), where plant assemblages are dominated by domesticated crops. However, due to the presence of ELONGATE DENTATE in the leaf tissue of several economically important sub-Saharan African grasses ([69](#)), we have chosen a more conservative approach and considered ELONGATE DENTATE to be anatomically non-diagnostic. Taxonomically, we have classified it as diagnostic of Poaceae.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Elongate echinate ([52](#), [59](#), [61](#), [63](#), [66](#)), Elongate serrated ([51](#)), Elongate sinuous ([57](#)), Tabular/parallelepipedal bodies with echinate margin ([62](#)), Long cell echinate ([67](#)), Elongate with echinate margin ([68](#)).

Fig. S30. ELONGATE DENTATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-c) Single celled phytolith. d) Articulated phytoliths. Scale bars are 10 μm .

ELONGATE DENDRITIC (ELO_DEN)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 14).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 14).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Maximum length ranges from 15 to 150 µm. Length to width ratio greater or equal to 2.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes were identified during analyses. ELONGATE DENDRITIC was more commonly found alone (Fig. S31a-b), despite the presence of some articulated silica skeletons (Fig. S31c).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Transitional forms with ELONGATE ENTIRE, ELONGATE SINUATE AND ELONGATE DENTATE were noted. These were always classified as ELONGATE DENDRITIC.

ELONGATE DENDRITIC is mainly produced because of silicification of epidermal long cells at the inflorescence of wild and domesticated grasses, where they form a continuum with ELONGATE DENTATE. They are present in a wide range of Poaceae subfamilies, including the BOP and PACMAD clades ([47](#)). We consider ELONGATE DENDRITIC to be diagnostic of Poaceae inflorescence, following the example of most phytolith studies in Africa ([51](#), [60](#), [61](#), [63](#), [64](#), [69–71](#)). Garnier et al. ([53](#)) is an exception and considers the morphotype as indicative of Poaceae leaves.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Elongate dendritic ([53](#), [61](#), [66](#)), Dendriform ([51](#), [63](#)), Dendritic long cells ([60](#), [64](#)).

Fig. S31. ELONGATE DENDRITIC from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-b) Single celled phytolith. c) Articulated phytoliths. Scale bars are 10 μm .

ELONGATE SINUATE (ELO_SIN)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. (47 Supplementary Data File 1: 10). Subtypes were named according to the shape of the long side margins and their projections.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. (47 Supplementary Data File 1: 10).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Maximum length ranges from 15 to 150 μm . Length to width ratio greater or equal to 2.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Eight subtypes were registered during analysis, according to the periodicity and amplitude of the margin undulations following Neumann et al. (47).

ELONGATE SINUATE REGULAR (ELO_SIN_REG) featured regularly spaced undulations, generally shorter than 2 μm , and of varying amplitude (Fig. S32a). Surface texture was almost always psilate. Mostly found isolated, but also as part of silica skeletons. No variants were recorded according to size.

ELONGATE SINUATE IRREGULAR (ELO_SIN_IRR) was characterized by sinuous margins showing irregularly spaced waves, shorter than 2 μm , and of varying amplitude (Fig. S32b). Texture of the surface was variable, but psilate surfaces were the most common. Commonly observed as single cells, though articulated forms were also recorded. No size variants were identified.

ELONGATE SINUATE CASTELLATE (ELO_SIN_CAS) showed a mostly regular pattern of square-to-rectangular projections (Fig. S32c). These were generally shorter than 2 μm and broader than tall. Surface texture was psilate in most cases. Single cells were very rare, and it appeared mostly in anatomical connection with other ELONGATE SINUATE CASTELLATE. No size variants were identified.

ELONGATE SINUATE CLAVATE (ELO_SIN_CLA) was characterized by a mostly regularly spaced pattern of club-shaped projections (constricted proximally, thicker at distal ends) along the margins (Fig. S32d). These were between 2 and 5 μm long. Surfaces were psilate. ELONGATE SINUATE CLAVATE was only recorded in anatomical connection. No size variants were identified.

ELONGATE SINUATE COLUMNAR (ELO_SIN_COL) had a regular pattern of taller than broad projections, featuring straight sides and square to rounded distal ends (Fig. S32e). Surface texture was psilate. ELONGATE SINUATE COLUMNAR appeared both as single cells and articulated skeletons. No variants were recorded according to size.

ELONGATE SINUATE WAVY (ELO_SIN_WAV) fits into Logan (70) description of “*Sorghum bicolor* Type 2 elongate dendritic”, which is characterized by irregular wavy margins with pointed-to-dendriiform peaks (Fig. S32f). ELONGATE SINUATE WAVY appeared both as single cells and articulated skeletons. No variants were recorded according to size.

ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE (ELO_SIN_INT) featured a regularly spaced pattern of undulated projections along the margins. According to the shape of the projections, variants were identified as Λ -shaped (Fig. S32g), β -shaped (Fig. S32h), Ω -shaped (Fig. S32i) and η -shaped (Fig. S32j) following previous publications (48–50). They were further classified from I to III in regards to the length and level of complexity of the undulations. Surface texture was always psilate. ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE were always found as silica skeletons.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Transitional forms of ELONGATE SINUATE REGULAR and ELONGATE SINUATE IRREGULAR with other elongate phytoliths occurred. ELONGATE ENTIRE/SINUATE were classified as ELONGATE SINUATE. ELONGATE SINUATE/DENTATE and ELONGATE SINUATE/DENDRITIC were considered as ELONGATE DENTATE and ELONGATE DENDRITIC respectively. Liminal forms between ELONGATE SINUATE COLUMNAR and ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE Ω -I were considered as ELONGATE SINUATE COLUMNAR when projections measured under 5 μ m long.

ELONGATE SINUATE REGULAR, ELONGATE SINUATE IRREGULAR, ELONGATE SINUATE CASTELLATE, ELONGATE SINUATE CLAVATE and ELONGATE SINUATE COLUMNAR are mainly produced in the leaf epidermis of Poaceae and Cyperaceae. However, they have also been documented in the leaf epidermis of Marantaceae, Pinaceae and Polypodiopsida (47). In this work, we consider these morphotypes to be diagnostic of Poaceae/Cyperaceae leaves and of Poaceae or Cyperaceae leaves -separately- when the articulated forms are accompanied by other typical morphotypes associated with either Poaceae (e.g. GSSCPs, ACUTE BULBOSUS, amongst others) or Cyperaceae family (e.g. CYPERACEAE CONE), following the example of previous studies (51, 61, 67). Indeed, these families are the highest producers of the mentioned subtypes of ELONGATE SINUATE, and they represent the main source of phytoliths in archaeological sites where agriculture is practiced. Furthermore, no morphotypes diagnostic of Marantaceae (72) or Polypodiopsida (73) were found in our assemblage and Pinaceae have not been recorded in the northern highlands of the Horn of Africa (27).

ELONGATE SINUATE WAVY has been associated with *Sorghum bicolor* by Logan (70). Authors such as Radomski and Neumann (74) or Out and Madella (75, 76) have also identified a similar morphotype from sorghum inflorescence bracts. However, a recent study by Hattingh (71) has shown ELONGATE SINUATE WAVY to also be present in three wild relatives of *Sorghum bicolor*, namely, *S. versicolor*, *S. bicolor* subsp. *arundinaceum* and *S. bicolor* subsp. *drummondii*. Similarly, Novello and Barboni (69) found the morphotype to be associated with several species of the Andropogoneae tribe –of which *Sorghum* spp. is a member. In this work, we have decided to interpret ELONGATE SINUATE WAVY as diagnostic of the tribe Andropogoneae, as there are other members of the tribe besides *Sorghum* sp. that are economically important: for example, *Andropogon* sp. is known to be used as fodder).

ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE are primarily formed in the epidermis of grass inflorescences. More specifically, they have been documented in the inflorescence bracts of both wild and domesticated species from the Panicoideae subfamily (21, 48–50, 75–82). Several studies have been conducted in order to refine taxonomic identification of ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE according to the shape of the projections and their level of complexity. In this regard, Λ -shaped projections have only been identified within 2 species of *Setaria* spp., namely *S. sphacelata* (50) and *S. verticillata* (83). Similarly, β -shaped E. s. INTERDIGITATE has been related to various species of *Echinochloa* sp. by several authors (49, 50, 80, 82). Regarding Ω -shaped INTERDIGITATE, level I projections have been identified in various wild species within the Paniceae tribe, including *Setaria*, *Oplismenus*, and *Paspalum* sp. (77, 81). On the contrary, Ω -II and Ω -III projections have only been identified within the genus *Setaria* (77, 81). Finally, η -shaped projections have been associated with *Panicum* and *Pennisetum* in several studies (50, 78, 81). We have followed the aforementioned interpretations to genus level except for E. s. INTERDIGITATE with Ω -shaped, level I projections, which we classified as diagnostic of the Paniceae tribe.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

ELONGATE SINUATE REGULAR / IRREGULAR: Elongate sinuate ([47](#), [61](#), [66](#)), Elongate with sinuated edges ([51](#)), Long cell wavy ([67](#)).

ELONGATE SINUATE CASTELLATE: Elongate castellate ([66](#)).

ELONGATE SINUATE CLAVATE: Elongate clavate ([66](#)).

ELONGATE SINUATE COLUMNAR: Elongate columellate ([66](#)).

ELONGATE SINUATE WAVY: Elongate dendritic ([70](#)), Dendritic long cells ([71](#), [75](#), [76](#)), Dendritics ([69](#), [71](#), [74](#)).

ELONGATE SINUATE INTERDIGITATE: Dendriform epidermal long cell with undulated patterns ([48](#), [77](#), [78](#)), Panicoid skeletons ([79](#)), Silica skeletons ([75](#), [76](#)), Dendritic long cell ([80](#)), Epidermal silica layer ([78](#)), Interdigitating ([81](#), [82](#)), Interdigitate ([50](#)).

Fig. S32. ELONGATE SINUATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) E. s. REGULAR b) E. s. IRREGULAR. c) E. s. CASTELLATE. d) E. s. CLAVATE. e) E. s. REGULAR COLUMNAR. f) E. s. WAVY. g) E. s. INTERDIGITATE Λ -shaped. h) E. s. INTERDIGITATE β -shaped. i) E. s. INTERDIGITATE Ω -shaped. j) E. s. INTERDIGITATE η -shaped. Scale bars are 10 μm .

BILOBATE (BIL)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 23).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 23).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Long axis generally 10-30 μm . Long axis length to lobe width in planar view (AL:LW) ratio greater or equal than 1.3.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Following Neumann et al. ([84](#)), six BILOBATE variants were identified taking into account absolute size and length of the shank. One variant (BILOBATE PLATEAUED) was also considered due to differences in its general shape.

BILOBATE VERY LARGE/VERY LONG SHANK (BIL_VLL_VLS) included the largest bilobated phytoliths, with a long axis greater than 26 μm and distinct shanks more than 7 μm (Fig. S33a). The inner periclinal surface (IPS) was generally of the same bilobated shape as the outer periclinal surface (OPS). OPS was usually slightly larger than IPS, hence showing a slightly carinated end view. The lobes in the OPS were characterized by their convex ends. Both surfaces were psilate and no ornamentation was observed.

BILOBATE LARGE/LONG SHANK (BIL_LL_LS) was characterized by a long axis between 18 and 26 μm , with distinct 4-7 μm shanks (Fig. S33b). IPS was mostly similar in bilobate shape and size to OPS, sometimes a little smaller featuring a somewhat trapeziform end view. Lobes in the OPS showed mainly convex, notched, and flat ends, more rarely concave and never scooped. Phytoliths with mixed different lobe shapes were common. No ornamentation was recorded on the psilate surfaces.

BILOBATE MEDIUM/LONG SHANK (BIL_ML_LS) featured a main axis of medium length, ranging between 10 and 18 μm , along with a distinct shank between 4 and 7 μm (Fig. S33c). IPS was of similar lobated shape to OPS, but smaller in size, usually exhibiting a subrounded end view. OPS ends were more commonly convex, although sometimes flat, notched, or mixed but never concave or scooped. Both OPS and IPS were psilate and no ornamentation was observed.

BILOBATE MEDIUM/SHORT SHANK (BIL_ML_SS) showed a 10-18 μm long axis together with a shorter than 4 μm , but still distinct, shank between the lobes (Fig. S33d). IPS was frequently equal in its bilobate shape and size to OPS, showing a rectangular or slightly trapeziform end view. The lobes in the OPS varied between flat, convex, notched, and mixed forms, but no concave or scooped phytoliths were recorded. All surfaces were psilate and no ornamentation was observed.

BILOBATE MEDIUM/CONSTRICTED SHANK (BIL_ML_CON) was characterized by medium-length long axis, between 10 and 18 μm , with a constricted shank (Fig. S33e). IPS was generally similar in bilobate shape and size to OPS, showing a subrounded end view. Lobes at the end of OPS were mostly convex, sometimes flat but never concave, notched, or scooped. Surfaces were all psilate with no ornamentation.

BILOBATE SMALL/CONSTRICTED SHANK (BIL_SL_CON) included the bilobate phytoliths with long axis smaller than 10 μm and constricted shanks (Fig. S33f). IPS was generally bilobate in shape and equal in size to OPS, with an end view varying from subrounded to square to trapeziform in shape. Lobes in OPS were mostly flat to slightly concave, more rarely convex, but never notched or scooped. Surfaces were psilate showing no ornamentation.

BILOBATE PLATEAUED (BIL_PLA) fits into Fredlund and Tieszen (85) description of “Lobate Stipa-type” (Fig. S33g). Long axis length ranged between 15 and 25 μm . IPS was smaller than OPS, with its shape varying from plateau-like to bilobated, hence forming trapeziform side and end views. OPS showed convex lobe ends and a reduced, almost constricted shank. All surfaces were psilate and no ornamentation was recorded.

BILOBATE was primarily found as single cells. It was also identified as part or silica skeleton, in anatomical connection with epidermal long cells (Fig. S33h).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

AL:LW ratio ≥ 1.3 was applied to differentiate BILOBATE from CROSS following ICPN 2.0. (47 Supplementary Data File 1: 23). Lobate phytoliths with additional nodes or lobes inserted in the shank were considered as POLYLOBATE.

BILOBATE form as a result of silica accumulation in the epidermal short cells of Poaceae culms, leaves and inflorescences. Traditionally, it was considered to be diagnostic of C4 Panicoid grasses. More recently, however, BILOBATE has been documented in several taxa from almost all grass subfamilies except for the early-diverging Anomochlooideae (47). Still, different variants can be associated to certain subclades based on previous knowledge of regional grass communities: for the African continent, palaeoecologists have tried to create more refined morphospaces for BILOBATE (62, 84, 86–88), though the results sometimes disagree and redundancy and multiplicity amongst wild grasses are high. Furthermore, it has been concluded that most of the ecological information is already captured by the main phytolith categories in both eastern and western Africa (84, 87). Due to the local character of the existing BILOBATE morphospaces and the complexity of harmonizing them, numerous authors (54, 60, 61, 63, 64, 68, 89, 90) have chosen to associate most size variants of BILOBATE with the Panicoideae subfamily –recognized as the primary producer of the morphotype in several publications (62, 84, 87, 88, 91). The existing research also shows the second most common BILOBATE producing subfamily to be Chloridoideae (69), especially in eastern Africa where over 45% of the surveyed Chloridoideae exhibited BILOBATE – including *Eleusine floccifolia* Spreng. and *Eragrostis macilenta* (A.Rich.) Steud (87). This is highly relevant to our case because Chloridoids such as *Eragrostis tef* –which exhibits over 25% of bilobates (74)– were domesticated in our study region. Indeed, BILOBATE has also been documented in *Eleusine coracana* (92), another member of the Chloridoideae subfamily, which is an eastern African domesticate, although its process of domestication is still not fully known. As such, we have considered BILOBATE LARGE/LONG SHANK, BILOBATE MEDIUM/LONG SHANK, BILOBATE MEDIUM/SHORT SHANK, BILOBATE MEDIUM/CONSTRICTED SHANK and BILOBATE SMALL/CONSTRICTED SHANK to be indicative of the Panicoideae/Chloridoideae subfamilies.

An important exception can be found in BILOBATE VERY LARGE-VERY LONG SHANK, which has been found to be diagnostic of Aristidoideae by different authors in different parts of the African continent and beyond (52, 84, 88, 93). Following the example of Yost et al. (64), we have chosen to be conservative since this exclusivity has not been confirmed in eastern Africa and classified BILOBATE VERY LARGE-VERY LONG SHANK as cf. Aristidoideae.

Finally, BILOBATE PLATEAUED was traditionally defined as indicative of the Stipeae C3 tribe (85). However, recent studies in Africa have shown the morphotype to be produced by other C3 taxa within the Pooideae, Ehrhartoideae and Danthonoideae subfamilies (87, 88, 94), and also by economically important C4 grasses such as *Sorghum* spp. (92) and *Eragrostis tef* (74), as well as other wild grasses from the Panicoideae subfamily (52, 62, 74, 84, 88, 94, 95). Overall, we have decided to consider BILOBATE PLATEAUED as diagnostic of the wider Poaceae family.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

BILOBATE: Bilobate short cell ([66](#)).

BILOBATE PLATEAUED: *Stipa*-type ([52](#), [84](#), [85](#), [87](#), [88](#), [94](#), [95](#)), Bilobate variant 5/6/others ([74](#)), Trapeziform bilobates ([62](#), [94](#)).

Fig. S33. BILOBATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) BILOBATE VERY LARGE/VERY LONG SHANK. b) BILOBATE LARGE/LONG SHANK. c) BILOBATE MEDIUM/LONG SHANK. d) BILOBATE MEDIUM/SHORT SHANK. e) BILOBATE MEDIUM/CONSTRICTED SHANK. f) BILOBATE SMALL/CONSTRICTED SHANK. g) BILOBATE PLATEAUED. h) Articulated BILOBATE with ELONGATE SINUATE. Scale bars are 10 μm .

POLYLOBATE (POL)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 24).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 24).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Main axis typically between 15 and 50 µm long.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Based on the shape and number of the castula-lobes, three subtypes were identified during the analyses:

POLYLOBATE NODULAR (POL_NOD) was characterized by the presence of an unpaired lobe forming a nodular outgrowth in one side of the castula (Fig. S34a). End lobes were mostly flat or notched, more rarely convex and never concave or scooped. Mixed end forms occurred. Surface texture was psilate.

POLYLOBATE TRILOBATE (POL_TRI) showed one paired lobe inserted in the castula (Fig. S34b). The castula-lobe was of the same size as the end lobes, which featured mostly flat and convex shapes, sometimes notches but never concave or scooped. Mixed end forms occurred. Surface texture was psilate.

POLYLOBATE MULTILOBATE (POL_MUL) featured two or more paired or unpaired lobes inserted in the castula (Fig. S34c). Castula lobes were of variable size, but never larger than the end lobes. End lobes were commonly convex or flat and never, concave, notched or scooped. Hybrid forms occurred. Mixed end forms occurred. Surface texture was psilate.

POLYLOBATE was mostly found as a single cell, but articulated forms were also recorded (Fig. S34d).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

POLYLOBATE was differentiated from BILOBATE due to the presence of additional nodes or lobes in the castula. POLYLOBATE was separated from CRENATE by its IPS and OPS lobed shaped and rounded side view (CRENATE presented rectangular IPS and a trapeziform shape in lateral view) as well as its well-defined lobes and castula (CRENATE castulae are less well-defined).

POLYLOBATE is known to be produced in the epidermal short cells of Poaceae culms, leaves, and inflorescences. Although it has been documented primarily in grasses of the Panicoideae and other PACMAD subfamilies in western Africa and the Sahel ([84](#), [86](#)), POLYLOBATE have also been documented amongst eastern and southern African Chloridoideae, as well as other C3-grasses including members of the Bambusoideae, Danthonoideae, Ehrhartoideae, and Pooideae subfamilies ([58](#), [87](#), [88](#), [96](#)). For all regions, publications agree that the number and shape of the lobes do not affect the taxonomic classification of POLYLOBATE. As such, we have considered all subtypes of POLYLOBATE to be diagnostic of Poaceae – even though most phytolith studies in the African associate them with the Panicoideae subclade ([53](#), [54](#), [63](#), [64](#), [68](#), [89](#), [90](#), [97](#)).

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

POLYLOBATE: Cylindrical polylobate ([58](#), [66](#)).

POLYLOBATE NODULAR: Nodular bilobate ([53](#), [84](#), [86](#), [97](#)), Nodular ([87](#)), Polylobate ([54](#), [84](#), [87](#), [88](#)).

POLYLOBATE TRILOBATE: Trilobate ([84](#), [86](#)), Polylobate ([53](#), [63](#), [64](#), [84](#), [87](#), [88](#), [96](#), [97](#)).

POLYLOBATE MULTILOBATE: Irregular complex bilobate ([84](#)), regular complex bilobate ([84](#)), Polylobate ([84](#), [87](#)).

Fig. S34. POLYLOBATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) POLYLOBATE NODULAR. b) POLYLOBATE TRILOBATE. c) POLYLOBATE MULTILOBATE. d) Articulated POLYLOBATE. Scale bars are 10 µm.

CROSS (CRO)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 26).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 24).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest axis measured between 8 and 30 μm . Long axis length to lobe width in planar view (AL:LW) ratio smaller than 1.3.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Three subtypes were identified according to the overall shape of the phytoliths (adapted from [98](#)). An additional subtype for 3-lobed crosses was considered following previous publications ([52](#), [62](#), [64](#), [74](#), [87](#)).

CROSS TABULAR (CRO_TAB) showed 4-lobed IPS and OPS of similar size, forming a tabular shaped side view (Fig. S35a). Surface texture was mostly psilate and usually without ornamentation, though more faceted specimens were also observed.

CROSS TRAPEZIFORM (CRO_TRA) was characterized by a smaller rectangular IPS than its 4-lobed OPS (Fig. S35b). The side view was trapeziform in shape. Surfaces were mostly psilate and ornamentation was very rare –faceted when present.

CROSS CARINATE (CRO_CAR) featured a very thin IPS in comparison to its 4-lobed OPS, having a keel shaped ridge and hence showing a tent-like shape in lateral view (Fig. S35c). Surface were always psilate and no ornamentation was observed.

CROSS TRIANGLE (CRO_TRI) comprised crosses with three lobes forming a triangular outline (Fig. S35d). 3-D shape was not considered, and both tabular and trapeziform variants existed. The texture of the phytolith surface was psilate and ornamentation was absent.

CROSS was primarily found as single cells.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Following Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 26), differentiation from BILOBATE was accomplished using an AL:LW ratio < 1.3 for CROSS.

CROSS forms in the epidermal short cells of Poaceae culms, leaves and inflorescence. It has been documented mainly in Panicoideae, but it is also present on other PACMAD (for example, Chloridoideae and the C3 Arundinoideae), Bambusoideae and Oryzoideae ([47](#)). More refined morphospaces of CROSS have been proposed by several authors since the late-1990s ([62](#), [74](#), [84](#), [86](#), [87](#), [98](#), [99](#)) allowing for finer classification and taxonomical association, but homogenization is still pending. CROSS is considered by most authors as diagnostic of Panicoideae subfamily ([53](#), [54](#), [59](#), [63](#), [64](#), [68](#), [84](#), [89](#), [90](#), [97](#), [100](#), [101](#)), as their members are the primary producers throughout the African continent ([51](#), [62](#), [84](#), [87](#), [91](#), [94](#)) whereas other taxonomic groups only produce them in very low numbers or display variants with very specific diagnostic features. However, CROSS TABULAR and CROSS TRAPEZIFORM has been recorded by Radomski and Neumann ([74](#)) in significant numbers (ca. 30%) on *Eragrostis tef* specimens, which is a very important domesticated Chloridoideae in our study region, hence we considered these three variants to be indicative of Panicoideae/Chloridoideae. The same authors, however, only recorded CROSS CARINATE on Panicoideae members and consequently we have considered this variant to be diagnostic of Panicoideae. As for CROSS TRIANGLE, we have followed the recommendation of Barboni and

Bremond ([87](#)), who noted that its presence in eastern African assemblages can be associated with Panicoideae and Chloridoideae.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

CROSS TABULAR: Cross V1 ([74](#)), Tabular cross ([62](#), [87](#)).

CROSS TRAPEZIFORM: Cross V5/6/others ([74](#)), Trapeziform cross ([62](#), [87](#)).

CROSS CARINATE: Cross V2 ([74](#), [98](#)).

CROSS TRIANGLE: Cross 3-lobed ([58](#), [87](#)), Triangular trilobate ([74](#)), Triangle cross ([84](#)).

Fig. S35. CROSS from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) CROSS TABULAR. b) CROSS TRAPEZIFORM. c) CROSS CARINATE. d) CROSS TRIANGLE. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

SADDLE (SAD)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 21).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 21).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest axis between 8 and 20 µm.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

According to 3D shape, three subtypes of SADDLE were documented during analyses:

SADDLE TABULAR (SAD_TAB) was characterized by having IPS and OPS with similar shape and size. Surface textures was psilate and no ornamentation was identified. Depending on the relative size of convex to concave faces, three variants were identified:

SADDLE TABULAR SYMMETRICAL (SAD_TAB_SYM) included phytoliths with equidimensional convex and concave faces (Fig. S36a).

SADDLE TABULAR LONG (SAD_TAB_LON) appeared with convex faces longer than the concave ones (Fig. S36b).

SADDLE TABULAR SHORT (SAD_TAB_SHO) showed convex faces shorter than concave faces (Fig. S36c).

SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM (SAD_TRA) included SADDLE with IPS smaller than OPS hence forming a trapeziform shape in lateral view. Surface was psilate and no ornamentation was identified. IPS was always saddle-shaped. However, two variants were identified according to the shape of OPS:

SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED (SAD_TRA_PLA) was defined as having an oblong, sometimes slightly constricted OPS (Fig. S36d).

SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM BILOBATED (SAD_TRA_BIL) featured OPS with a bilobated outlines (Fig. S36e).

SADDLE COLLAPSED (SAD_COL) was characterized by a very concave IPS, seemingly “collapsing” towards OPS in lateral view (Fig. S36f). Surface textures were psilate and no ornamentation was identified. No variants were differentiated during observation.

SADDLE was mostly found as single cell, but articulated forms were also documented (Fig. S36g).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

SADDLE and its variants are formed within epidermal short cells of grass culm, leaves and inflorescences. Traditionally, they have been considered to be produced mostly by Chloridoideae ([85](#), [102](#)).

On the one hand, the more “classic” subtype SADDLE TABULAR and its variants are generally associated with Chloridoideae, but other grass subfamilies such as the Bambusoideae, as well as non-chloridoid C3 and C4 PACMAD also produce them –especially SADDLE TABULAR SHORT ([47](#))– although in much lower numbers ([69](#), [84](#), [87](#), [91](#), [96](#), [103](#)). Accordingly, we have considered SADDLE TABULAR SYMMETRICAL and SADDLE TABULAR LONG as diagnostic of Chloridoideae following the example of several authors ([51](#), [52](#), [54](#), [56](#), [61](#), [63](#), [64](#), [68](#), [84](#), [87](#), [89](#), [90](#), [97](#), [100](#), [101](#), [104](#)), whereas SADDLE TABULAR SHORT was associated with the wider Poaceae following the recommendation of Barboni and Bremond ([87](#)).

On the other hand, SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM variants are also common in non-chloridoideae grasses. In fact, SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED was traditionally considered as potentially diagnostic of the genus *Phragmites* (Arundinoideae) (98, 105–107, cited in 63 Supplementary Online Materials S1: 4). In this sense, more recent studies have found SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED also to be present in members of the Aristidoideae, Chloridoideae, Danthonioideae, and Panicoideae subfamilies (84, 88). Yost et al. (63 Supplementary Online Materials S1: 5) introduced five criteria to be met in order to separate *Phragmites* sp. from other taxa using SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED. Since our SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED did not consistently meet all the listed criteria, we chose to consider the morphotype only as indicative of the wider Poaceae family. As for SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM BILOBATED, it has been documented mainly within the Chloridoideae and Panicoideae subfamilies (69, 84). Even though its presence has also been recorded in *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud. by Novello et al. (62), the authors found a statistically relevant association between SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM BILOBATED and C4 xerophytic grasses –*Phragmites australis* is a water-loving species– and thereby we have classified it as indicative of cf. Chloridoideae/Panicoideae.

Finally, SADDLE COLLAPSED have been sometimes associated with the Bambusoideae subfamily (53, 97, 103, 108). In eastern Africa, some bamboo species such *Oxytenanthera abyssinica* (A.Rich.) Munro –referred to as lowland bamboo in Ethiopia– have been found to produce SADDLE COLLAPSED (84, 97). By contrast, others, e.g. *Yushania alpina* (K.Schum.) W.C.Lin – known as highland bamboo in Ethiopia– only seem produce saddle-like phytoliths in very small amounts (63 but see 97 for contradictory results). Barboni and Bremond (87) showed that SADDLE COLLAPSED are also common amongst eastern African Chloridoideae grasses and, in another publication, Bremond et al. (59) found SADDLE COLLAPSED to be practically insignificant (< 1%) in soil samples under bamboo stands of *Arundinaria alpina* K.Schum (a synonym of *Yushania alpina* (K.Schum.) W.C.Lin) from Mount Kenya. Since our samples come from archaeological sites located at over 2000 m.a.s.l., we have considered SADDLE COLLAPSED to be indicative of cf. Chloridoideae.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

SADDLE TABULAR SYMMETRICAL: Saddle symmetrical (87), S-1 (62).

SADDLE TABULAR LONG: Saddle long (87), S-3 (62), Saddle squat (84).

SADDLE TABULAR SHORT: Saddle short (87), S-2 (62), Saddle tall (84).

SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED: Wide-saddle (105), Saddle-topped short trapezoids (106), Concave rondel (107), S-4 (62), Saddle plateaued (63, 64, 84, 98).

SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM BILOBATED: S-5 (62).

Fig. S36. SADDLE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) SADDLE TABULAR SYMMETRICAL. b) SADDLE TABULAR LONG. c) SADDLE TABULAR SHORT. d) SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM PLATEAUED. e) SADDLE TRAPEZIFORM BILOBATED. f) SADDLE COLLAPSED. g) Articulated SADDLE. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

RONDEL (RON)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 29).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 29).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

OPS diameter typically 6-20 μm .

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Three, further divided into five, subtypes of RONDEL were recorded according to 3D shape and IPS surface ornamentation. An additional variant according to size was considered following Barboni and Bremond ([87](#)).

RONDEL TABULAR (RON_TAB) included RONDEL phytoliths with a rounded IPS equal in size to OPS. According to type of ornamentation, it was further divided into:

RONDEL TABULAR PSILATE (RON_TAB_PSI) showing both IPS and OPS with flat, psilate surface (Fig. S37a).

RONDEL TABULAR CORNICULATE (RON_TAB_COR) featured a corniculate IPS, that is, presenting two or more horned projections (Fig. S37b).

RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM (RON_TRA) was characterized by an IPS smaller than the OPS, hence forming a trapeziform shape on side view. It was further divided following the ornamentation criteria into: RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM PSILATE (RON_TRA_PSI) (Fig. S37c) and RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM CORNICULATE (RON_TRA_COR) (Fig. S37d).

RONDEL CARINATE (RON_CAR) had a rounded OPS with a keeled IPS, giving it a tent-like shape on side view (Fig. S37e). Surface texture was psilate and no ornamentation was recorded.

Finally, we recorded the presence of a size variant including RONDEL with an OPS of more than 15 μm (Fig. S37f). These included members of RONDEL TABULAR PSILATE and RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM PSILATE and have been associated with C3-grass in eastern Africa by Barboni and Bremond ([87](#)). As such, we counted them separately and named them C3 RONDEL (RON_C3) –see below for a discussion.

For the most part, RONDEL was found as single cells but articulated forms were also recorded (Fig. S37g).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

RONDEL could be separated from TRAPEZOID as the former showed a rounded OPS whereas the latter featured a quadratic to square OPS.

RONDEL is formed in the epidermal short cell of culms, leaves and inflorescences in members of the Poaceae family. Often, it has been associated with the Pooideae subfamily ([63](#)), although recent studies on Sub-Saharan grasses have recorded a broader RONDEL morphospace, with different subtypes redundantly present in a wider range of Poaceae subfamilies ([69](#), [74](#), [84](#), [87](#), [94](#)), including the C4 Panicoideae (e.g. *Andropogon*, *Sorghum*, *Sorghastrum* spp.) and Chloridoideae (e.g. *Eragrostis*, *Sporobolus* spp.). Consequently, we have considered all RONDEL subtypes to be indicative of Poaceae. An exception was made after Barboni and Bremond ([87](#)), who showed RONDEL with OPS size over 15 μm to be diagnostic of high-elevation C3 temperate Pooideae grasses regardless of other morphological features. We chose to follow this recommendation and considered the C3 RONDEL variant as diagnostic of Pooideae.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

RONDEL TABULAR CORNICULATE: Horned tower ([94](#)), Rondel corniculate ([84](#)).

RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM CORNICULATE: Rondel saddle-like ([74](#)).

RONDEL CARINATE: Keeled ([94](#)), Rondel keeled ([63](#), [64](#), [84](#)).

Fig. S37. RONDEL from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) RONDEL TABULAR PSILATE. b) RONDEL TABULAR CORNICULATE. c) RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM PSILATE. d) RONDEL TRAPEZIFORM CORNICULATE. e) RONDEL CARINATE. f) RONDEL C3. g) Articulated RONDEL. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

TRAPEZOID (TRZ).

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 30).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 30).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest axis mostly 6-30 μm .

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were identified during analyses.

TRAPEZOID was almost always found as a single cell (Fig. S38a). Articulated forms were rare, but present (Fig. S38b).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

TRAPEZOID was separated from RONDEL, CRENATE and ELONGATE ENTIRE following ICPN 2.0. criteria ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 30).

As a grass silica short cell morphotype, TRAPEZOID is formed in the epidermis of Poaceae culms, leaves and inflorescence. Even though it has been often considered as indicative of Pooideae ([61](#), [68](#), [88](#), [91](#), [96](#)), the redundancy of TRAPEZOID amongst eastern African grass subfamilies is very high ([87](#)). As such, we considered TRAPEZOID to be indicative of Poaceae.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Trapeziform short cell ([66](#)).

Fig. S38. TRAPEZIFORM from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) Single-celled TRAPEZIFORM. b) Articulated TRAPEZIFORM. Scale bars are 10 μm .

CRENATE (CRE).

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 27).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 27).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Long axis mostly 15-50 µm.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Two subtypes were identified during analysis according to the shape of the OPS sides:

CRENATE SINUATE (CRE_SIN) showed OPS featuring sinuate outline (Fig. S39a-b).

CRENATE CRENATE (CRE_CRE) was characterized by OPS with crenate margins (Fig. S39c-d).

Both subtypes of CRENATE were always found isolated.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

CRENATE and POLYLOBATE were separated using ICPN 2.0. ([47](#)) criteria as described above.

CRENATE SINUATE and CRENATE CRENATE are known to be formed by silicification of epidermal short cells of Poaceae culms, leaves and inflorescences. It is primarily found within the Pooideae subfamily though it has also been recorded in low frequencies in other PACMAD grasses and early diverging Poaceae ([47](#)). Even so, most authors working in Africa have considered it to be diagnostic of Pooideae ([61](#), [63](#), [64](#), [87](#), [88](#), [90](#), [94](#), [109](#)). In this research, we followed the recommendation by Barboni and Bremond ([87](#)) for eastern African studies and considered it to be diagnostic of the Pooideae subfamily.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

CRENATE SINUATE: Trapeziform sinuate ([61](#), [63](#), [64](#), [66](#), [87](#), [94](#), [109](#)), Rectangular trapezoid ([88](#)), Oblong trapeziform sinuate ([90](#)).

CRENATE CRENATE: Trapeziform polylobate ([61](#), [62](#), [66](#)), Oblong trapeziform polylobate ([90](#)).

Fig. S39. CRENATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-b) CRENATE SINUATE. c-d) CRENATE CRENATE. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

PAPILLATE (PAP)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 3-4).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 4).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest diameter between 10-25 μm .

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were identified during analyses.

PAPILLATE was commonly found in anatomical connection with different ELONGATE types, but isolated specimens were also recorded (Fig. S40a-e)

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

PAPILLATE is produced as a result of the silicification of a specific hair cell type present in the inflorescence bracts of Poaceae ([47](#)). Consequently, we considered PAPILLATE as diagnostic of Poaceae inflorescence, in agreement with previous publications ([61](#), [67](#), [108](#)).

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Papillae ([66](#)).

Fig. S40. PAPILLATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-b) Single-celled PAPILLATE. c-e) Articulated PAPILLATE. Scale bars are 10 μm .

ACUTE BULBOSUS (ACU_BUL)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 2).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 2).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Mostly between 10-60 µm long.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were identified during analyses.

ACUTE BULBOSUS was always found isolated (Fig. S41a-f).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

When ACUTE BULBOSUS featured fusiform antapex, it was differentiated from ACICULAR FUSIFORM due to the presence of an acute apex, regardless of its size.

ACUTE BULBOSUS is mainly produced as a result of silicification of grass hair cells. It is also present in some non-grass monocotyledons and dicotyledons, but in much lower frequencies ([47](#)). As Poaceae are the main producers of ACUTE BULBOSUS, phytolith specialist working in Africa have usually considered them diagnostic of grasses ([51](#), [56](#), [58](#), [64](#), [68](#), [87](#), [89](#), [91](#), [97](#), [100](#)). Other authors, however, have considered them to represent Poaceae/Cyperaceae ([53](#), [63](#)), or even to be non-diagnostic ([52](#), [62](#)). Recent studies have shown ACUTE BULBOSUS to be present in several Sub-Saharan species of the Cyperaceae family ([62](#), [110](#)). As such, we have considered them to be indicative of Poaceae/Cyperaceae as they are the highest producers of this morphotype and represent the main input of ACUTE BULBOSUS into archaeological sites where agriculture is practiced.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Point-shaped ([52](#), [53](#), [91](#)), Hair ([51](#), [56](#), [89](#)), Trichome ([52](#), [63](#), [100](#)), Acicular hair cell ([58](#), [66](#), [87](#), [110](#)), Scutiform ([97](#), [110](#)), Acicular type (Aci-2) ([62](#)), Acicular type (Aci-1) ([69](#)), Prickle ([68](#)), Trichome (Poaceae type) ([64](#)).

Fig. S41. ACUTE BULBOSUS from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

ACICULAR FUSIFORM (CYL_FUS)

- **Rationale for naming:**

A morphological name was used because it is taxonomically redundant and the anatomic origin of ACICULAR FUSIFORM is still unclear. The name included the descriptive terms of the tridimensional and bidimensional shapes –in that order– of the morphotype according to ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 2).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

Solid silica spindle-shaped body with circular to ellipsoidal cross-section, thicker in the middle and asymmetrically narrowing towards the ends. Surface texture varies from scrobiculate to psilate to baculate.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest axis typically 30-60 µm long.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were identified during analyses. It was always found isolated (Fig. S42a-b).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

ACICULAR FUSIFORM was separated from ACUTE BULBOSUS due to the absence of an acute apex.

ACICULAR FUSIFORM has been sometimes associated with woody dicotyledon plants ([56](#), [103](#), [111](#)), but its taxonomical association and anatomical origin are still under discussion. On the one hand, Esteban et al. ([68](#)) proposed it to be associated with epidermal hair cells within eudicotyledons, but their anatomical origin still needs to be further explored. On the other hand, Novello et al. ([62](#)) recorded it within several African members of the Poaceae family. As such, we have decided to consider ACICULAR FUSIFORM as non-diagnostic.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Clavate ([111](#)), Acicular type (Aci-1) ([62](#)).

Fig. S42. ACUTE FUSIFORM from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

SPHEROID PSILATE (SPH_PSI)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. (47).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. (47).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Diameter 3-20 µm long.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were identified during analyses. SPHEROID PSILATE was always found isolated (Fig. S43a-c).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

SPHEROID PSILATE is formed as the result of silica infilling of epidermal and parenchyma cells, as well as within tissues in the reproductive organs of both monocotyledons and dicotyledons (47). Despite its ubiquity amongst plant tissues of several taxonomic groups, some authors have considered it to be diagnostic of arboreal vegetation as some woody dicotyledons produce SPHEROID PSILATE in abundance (56, 60, 64, 67, 89, 109). Still, most phytolith studies in Africa have shown SPHEROID PSILATE to be taxonomically and anatomically redundant and thereby of very low taxonomic value (51–54, 59, 63, 100, 111–114). In this research, we have taken a conservative position and considered SPHEROID PSILATE as non-diagnostic.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Globular psilate (66).

Fig. S43. SPHEROID PSILATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. Scale bars are 10 μm .

SPHEROID ECHINATE (SPH_ECH)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. (47).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. (47).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Diameter between 2 and 25 µm long.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes were identified during analysis. Two variants according to size were recorded:

SPHEROID ECHINATE ZINGIBERALES (SPH_ECH_ZIN) always measured less than 5 µm long (Fig. S44a).

SPHEROID ECHINATE ARECACEAE (SPH_ECH_ARE) showed diameters between 5 and 25 µm (Fig. S44b-h).

SPHEROID ECHINATE was mostly found isolated. Articulated forms were rarely present.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

SPHEROID ECHINATE was differentiated from SPHEROID ORNATE by the presence of well-defined conical spines throughout the entire surface of the phytolith.

SPHEROID ECHINATE is primarily formed in the vegetative and reproductive organs of Arecaceae, as well as in leaves of Bromeliaceae (47). Because of the almost complete absence of Bromeliaceae in the Old World (only one species in western Africa), most scholars working in Africa have considered SPHEROID ECHINATE to be diagnostic of palms (Arecaceae) (51–54, 59–61, 63, 64, 67, 68, 91, 101, 103, 108, 109, 111, 112, 114, 115). We have followed their example and considered the larger SPHEROID ECHINATE variant to be diagnostic of Arecaceae. However, a smaller version “globular micro-echinate” has been recorded in some genera of the Zingiberales order (diameter up to 3 µm, whereas Arecaceae produce SPHEROID ECHINATE of at least 6 µm), for example, *Phenakospermum* or *Zingiber* spp. (72). Consequently, we have considered the smaller variant to be diagnostic of Zingiberales.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

SPHEROID ECHINATE ARECACEAE: Circular crenate (91), Spherical Palmae phytolith with spinulose surface (51), Globular echinate (53, 54, 59–61, 63, 64, 66, 101, 103, 108, 109, 111, 112), Globular echinate, Arecaceae (palms) (52).

SPHEROID ECHINATE ZINGIBERALES: Globular microechinate (72).

Fig. S44. SPHEROID ECHINATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) SPHEROID ECHINATE ZINGIBERALES. b-h) SPHEROID ECHINATE ARECACEAE. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

SPHEROID ORNATE (SPH_ORN)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. (47).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. (47).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Diameter 10-50 µm long, varying significantly between subtypes.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Three subtypes were identified during analyses according to surface ornamentation:

SPHEROID ORNATE PLICATE (SPH_ORN_PLI) featured an irregularly folded surface, often forming a spiny-like texture (Fig S45a). Size varied between 10 and 25 µm.

SPHEROID ORNATE VERRUCATE (SPH_ORN_VER) was characterized by showing irregular wart-like processes (Fig S45b). Diameter was 10 to 20 µm long.

SPHEROID ORNATE NODULATE (SPH_ORN_NOD) showed a complex surface composed of irregular nodules or spheres (Fig S45c). Size was commonly over 30 µm.

SPHEROID ORNATE was always found isolated.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

SPHEROID ORNATE has been traditionally identified mainly in wood, bark, leaves and fruits of woody dicotyledons. As a result, some authors have use SPHEROID ORNATE as a marker of arboreal vegetation (53, 54, 56, 59, 60, 63, 67, 89, 91, 100, 101, 103, 108, 112). However, other studies have recorded a significant number of SPHEROID ORNATE within the vegetative tissue of some herbaceous monocots, for example within the order Zingiberales (51, 72, 116). In fact, several authors indicate that SPHEROID ORNATE PLICATE are typical in the Marantaceae, Cannaceae, Costaceae and Strelitziaceae families of the Zingiberales order (47). Following this information, we have considered SPHEROID ORNATE PLICATE to be indicative of Zingiberales. Studies on SPHEROID ORNATE VERRUCATE (116, 117) have shown that dicotyledon plants produce smaller phytoliths (ca. 3 to 9/10 µm) than monocots in the Zingiberales order (10-30 µm) –although Zingiberales might show an even greater range according to Chen and Smith (72). Since all SPHEROID ORNATE VERRUCATE recorded in our analysis were at least 10 µm or greater, we have chosen to consider it to be indicative of cf. Zingiberales. Finally, SPHEROID ORNATE NODULATE was classified as diagnostic of woody dicotyledons in accordance with the results of Collura and Neumann's (113) study of western African wood and bark phytoliths.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Circular rugose (91), Globular granulate (66), Verrucate phytolith (116), Decorated sphere (116), Spherical rugose (117), Decorated Globular, with various patterns of surface sculpturing (72), Globular decorated (64).

SPHEROID ORNATE PLICATE: Spherical irregularly angled or folded (51).

SPHEROID ORNATE VERRUCATE: Spherical verrucose (51).

SPHEROID ORNATE NODULATE: Aggregates nodular (113).

Fig. S45. SPHEROID ORNATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) SPHEROID ORNATE PPLICATE. b) SPHEROID ORNATE VERRUCATE. c) SPHEROID ORNATE NODULATE. Scale bars are 10 μm .

COMMELINACEAE CONICAL (COM_CON)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Because COMMELINACEAE CONICAL is known to be produced only by members of the Commelinaceae family, a taxonomic name has been given. A second term was used to describe the overall 3D shape, a trait common to the recorded subtypes.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

COMMELINACEAE CONICAL is a broad morphotype that encompasses various phytolith types defined as “Group 2, flat polygonal prisms with a conical top” by Eichhorn et al. (118). According to these authors, this morphotype is characterized by the polygonal shape of their bases, forming a prism which is topped by a truncated cone of varying height. This upper conical part can show different shapes, from concave to flat to convex.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Mostly between 10 and 25 µm wide and 5 to 12 µm tall, though measurements varied amongst subtypes. See Eichhorn et al. (118: 301-302) for more detailed data on morphometric variation.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

During analysis, two of the four types described by Eichhorn et al. (118) were recorded:

COMMELINACEAE CONICAL CYANOTIS (COM_CON_CYA) fits into the *Cyanotis* type described by Eichhorn et al. (118: 307). It is characterized by a flat to convex upper cone and a psilate surface (Fig. S46a-b).

COMMELINACEAE CONICAL COMMELINA (COM_CON_COM) corresponds to the type associated by Eichhorn et al. (118: 307) to *Commelina subulata* Roth. This subtype shows a concave upper conical body and the presence of granulate surface ornamentation (Fig. S46b-c).

COMMELINACEAE CONICAL were always found isolated.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Following Eichhorn et al. (118), COMMELINACEAE CONICAL was separated from CYPERACEAE CONICAL mainly due the specific features of the central protuberance and the absence of surface ornamentation.

COMMELINACEAE CONICAL is known to be produced in the reproductive organs of the Commelinaceae family, specifically within the seed coat of *Pollia condensate* C.B.Clarke, *Murdannia simplex* (Vahl) Brenan, *Floscopa* spp., *Cyanotis* spp. and *Commelina subulata* Roth (118). COMMELINACEAE CONICAL was identified in fluvial sediments of western Africa (53), but it has not been documented in eastern Africa to date. In our research, we have chosen to remain at the genus level and considered the identified subtypes to be diagnostic of their respective genera.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Flat polygonal prisms with a conical top (118).

COMMELINACEAE CONICAL CYANOTIS: *Cyanotis* type (118), *Cyanotis lanata* type (53).

Fig. S46. COMMELINACEAE CONICAL from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-b) COMMELINACEAE CONICAL CYANOTIS. c-d) COMMELINACEAE CONICAL COMMELINA. Scale bars are 10 μm .

COMMELINACEAE PRISMATIC (COM_PRI)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Because COMMELINACEAE PRISMATIC is known to be produced only by members of the Commelinaceae family, a taxonomic name has been given. A second term was used to describe the overall 3D shape.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

This morphotype coincides with “Group 3” by Eichhorn et al. (118: 307) which is described as a solid body with dissimilar poles, having a subcylindric base and a polygonal upper part with a subconical top.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Mostly between 10 and 20 µm wide and 5 to 15 µm tall. See Eichhorn et al. (118: 301-302) for more detailed data on morphometric variation.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were recorded during analysis. They were always found isolated (Fig. S47a-e).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

COMMELINACEAE PRISMATIC is formed within the reproductive organs of certain species of the Commelinaceae (mainly *Commelina* spp.) and Marantaceae (for example, *Marantochloa*, *Maranta* and *Calathea* spp.) (72, 118). According to Eichhorn et al. (118), however, these families can be separated due to differences in size –Commelinaceae phytoliths being much smaller– and/or top shape (Commelinaceae shows concave tops, whereas Marantaceae features flat tops). As so, the morphotype was considered to be diagnostic of Commelinaceae in subsequent studies on different parts of Africa (53, 62–64). It is noteworthy that this has been questioned by Chen and Smith (72) who, after studying phytolith variability amongst Zingiberales, argued that more studies are needed to confirm that separation between the two is possible. Following the example of recent studies in eastern Africa by Yost et al. (63, 64), we have considered COMMELINACEAE PRISMATIC as diagnostic of Commelinaceae, as all the phytoliths in our assemblage present concave tops and fit in Eichhorn et al. (118) size ranges.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Commelina type (53), Commelinaceae-type phytolith (Pol-1) (62), Prismatic domed cylinder (63, 64).

Fig. S47. COMMELINACEAE PRISMATIC ANISOPOLAR from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. Scale bars are 10 μm .

CYPERACEAE CONICAL (CYP_CON)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Because this morphotype is only known to be produced only by members of the Cyperaceae family, a taxonomic name has been assigned. A second term was used to describe the overall 3D shape.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

Solid, conical phytoliths with isodiametric or with four- to seven-sided polygonal bases, sometimes with short projections in its margins (65). Side view showed variation from truncated to pointed tops. Surface texture varied between subtypes from psilate to granulate.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Typically 10-25 µm wide and 5-10 µm tall.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Two main subtypes were recorded during analysis, and were named according to their surface ornamentation:

CYPERACEAE CONICAL PSILATE (CYP_CON_PSI) featured isodiametric bases with psilate texture. Tops appeared both truncated and pointed. It was mostly found articulated (Fig. S48a).

CYPERACEAE CONICAL GRANULATE (CYP_CON_GRA) mostly showed polygonal bases with granulate texture, sometimes including lateral margin projections. Both truncated and pointed top ends were recorded. They were always documented isolated (Fig. S48b-f).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Eichorn et al. (118) was followed to differentiate between COMMELINACEAE CONICAL and CYPERACEAE CONICAL as stated above.

The members of the Cyperaceae family produce large numbers of phytoliths in the epidermal cells of vegetative and reproductive structures. Specifically, numerous African species are known to produce CYPERACEAE CONICAL PSILATE in their culms and leaves, whereas CYPERACEAE CONICAL GRANULATE is mainly produced in their fruits (65). As such, we have considered CYPERACEAE CONICAL PSILATE to be diagnostic of Cyperaceae leaves/culms, and CYPERACEAE CONICAL GRANULATE of Cyperaceae fruits.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

CYPERACEAE CONICAL PSILATE: Cyperaceae leaf/culm cone (65)

CYPERACEAE CONICAL GRANULATE: Polygonal granulate achene (65), *Cyperus* type (65).

Fig. S48. CYPERACEAE CONICAL from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) CYPERACEAE CONICAL PSILATE. b-f) CYPERACEAE CONICAL GRANULATE. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

STOMATE (STO)

- **Rationale for naming:**

STOMATE is a *nomen conservandum* from Esau's work *Plant Anatomy* (119). In plant science, stomata are pores that regulate the flow of gasses in and out of the plant. The term, however, is collectively applied to name the entire stomatal complex, that is, the pore itself and the two guard cells that surround it. As the morphotype can be unambiguously attributed to this tissue, an anatomical name was assigned.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See Evert (120) for a detailed anatomical description of the stomatal complex. In our assemblage, STOMATE includes a pair of dumbbell-shaped guard cells, each surrounded by one subsidiary cell (Fig. S49a). Sometimes it can also include silicified substomatal cells attached to its base (Fig. S49b).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest axis typically 15-25 μm .

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were recorded during analysis. Both isolated and articulated forms were recorded (Fig. S49a-c).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

Stomata are present in all the aerial parts of both monocotyledon and dicotyledon plants (120). Still, they are more abundant on leaves, reason why STOMATE has traditionally been considered diagnostic of leaf tissue. It is noteworthy that stomata from dicotyledon plants show crescent-shaped guard cells with blunt ends, whereas the Poaceae –and a few other monocots– feature dumbbell-shaped guard cells (120). Since Poaceae are responsible for the main input of phytoliths in agricultural sites, we have considered STOMATE to be diagnostic of Poaceae leaves, following the example of previous publications (63, 64, 67).

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Stomata (67), Stomatal complex (63, 64).

Fig. S49. STOMATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) Single-celled STOMATE. b-c) Articulated STOMATE. Scale bars are 10 μm

MESOPHYLL (MES)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Since the morphotype can be unambiguously attributed to mesophyll plant cells, an anatomical term was preferred.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

MESOPHYLL is highly variable in shape, from rounded to ellipsoidal, to subrounded to squared. It often appears in anatomical connection, forming a honeycomb-like structure ([116](#)).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Typically 2-5 μm .

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were identified during analyses. MESOPHYLL was solely recorded as an articulated body (Fig. S50a-b).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

MESOPHYLL was separated from SPHEROID PSILATE due to its articulated state and variable shape.

MESOPHYLL is formed in the internal ground tissue between the epidermal layers of plant leaves. It is mainly present in dicotyledon plants ([116](#)), and hence we have considered it to be indicative of leaves from dicotyledonous taxa.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Mesophyll ([66](#)).

Fig. S50. MESOPHYLL from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. Scale bars are 10 μm .

TRACHERY (TRA)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 16).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 16).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length 15-150 µm and width 5-25 µm.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were recorded during analyses. TRACHERY was mostly found isolated though articulated forms were also recorded (Fig. S51a-d).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

TRACHERY was separated from SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID as the latter are more irregular in shape ([47](#)).

TRACHERY is formed in the interior of plants vascular tissue, mainly as a result of the silicification of conductive cells from the primary xylem ([47](#), [113](#)). The taxonomic value of TRACHERY is low, as it is present in a wide range of monocotyledonous and dicotyledonous plants ([47](#)). Still, it has been commonly used as a marker of woody plants by several authors ([52-54](#), [56](#), [60](#), [68](#), [101](#)), as Poaceae usually produce a specific type of tracheids -very straight and pitted (see [47](#), Figure 7A). Since this type of tracheids are not present in our assemblage, we have chosen to follow the example of the majority and considered TRACHERY as indicative of dicotyledonous plants. Following the recommendation by Collura and Neumann ([113](#)), we decided to consider it to be anatomically non-diagnostic.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Tracheid ([66](#)).

Fig. S51. TRACHEARY from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. Scale bars are 10 μm .

TABULAR (TAB).

- **Rationale for naming:**

Since a taxonomical or anatomical attribution is not possible, we chose to use a morphological name. The term expresses the three-dimensional shape of the morphotype.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

TABULAR encompasses a number of solid, relatively thin morphotypes with two parallel flat faces. Two-dimensional shape varies from polygonal to irregular. Surface texture is mostly psilate.

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Highly variant, but typically from 10 to 50 µm.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

Two subtypes were identified according to overall shape, following Piperno (116):

TABULAR POLYGONAL (TAB_POL) showed a generally polygonal outline with entire margins (Fig. S52a).

TABULAR AMOEBOID (TAB_AMO) featured irregular phytoliths with sinuate margins (Fig. S52b-c).

Both morphotypes were mostly found isolated. Articulated forms were very rarely documented.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

TABULAR POLYGONAL was separated from BLOCKY as the latter shows roughly equal width and thickness, whereas TABULAR POLYGONAL is much thinner.

TABULAR formed in the epidermal cells of several plant taxa. Indeed, the diagnostic value of TABULAR POLYGONAL is very low and we have considered it to be non-diagnostic, following the recommendation by Piperno (116). On the contrary, TABULAR AMOEBOID is mainly found in dicotyledon plants, both woody and herbaceous (121). Even though Piperno (116) argues that TABULAR AMOEBOID has also been identified within monocots, studies in eastern and central Africa (63, 64, 89, 111, 122) have commonly associated it with dicotyledon plants and we have chosen to follow their example.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

TABULAR POLYGONAL: Polyhedral (116), Epidermal polygonal (111), Plates (122).

TABULAR AMOEBOID: Jigsaw-puzzle (121), Jigsaw (107), Thick plate with sinuous contour (113), Epidermal jig-saw (89, 111), Wavy margin plate (63), Anticlinal epidermis sheet (64).

Fig. S52. TABULAR from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a) TABULAR POLYGONAL. b) Single-celled TABULAR AMOEBOID. c) Articulated TABULAR AMOEBOID. Scale bars are 10 μm .

SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID (SMA_SCL)

- **Rationale for naming:**

As it can be associated unambiguously with a specific plant tissue, an anatomical name was given. Noteworthy, the use of shape as descriptor was avoided following recommendation by Collura and Neumann ([113](#)) for sclerenchyma associated phytoliths.

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID encompasses a broad group of phytoliths (Fig. S53a-n), from elongates to cylindroids to irregulars with external protrusions, with entire to sinuate to echinate and both with and without surface ornamentation (see [113](#) for further details).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest axis 40-100 μm .

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were proposed during analyses.

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

The identification of SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID was based on comparisons with previously published morphotypes ([53](#), [56](#), [63](#), [68](#), [113](#)).

SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID is mainly formed on the cortex of the aerial vegetative part of dicotyledonous plants. They occur in a large number of dicot families but are mostly restricted to trees and shrubs ([116](#)). Consequently, they have usually been used as a marker of wood and bark from dicotyledon plants ([53](#), [56](#), [60](#), [61](#), [63](#), [64](#), [67](#), [68](#), [101](#), [108](#)). A study of phytoliths in western African plants showed SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID to be completely absent in wood, but common in dicotyledon bark, leaves and fruits ([113](#)). Much work is needed in order to further refine the SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID morphospace, and consequently we have decided to be conservative and consider it to be taxonomically diagnostic of dicotyledon plants, but anatomically non-diagnostic.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Brachiform ([115](#)), Sclereid ([53](#), [54](#), [56](#), [60](#), [61](#), [63](#), [64](#), [67](#), [101](#), [108](#), [113](#)), Cilindric faceted ([53](#)), Cylindric geniculate psilate ([53](#)), Polyhedral faceted ([53](#)), Ellipsoid with outgrowths ([53](#)), Blocky faceted ([54](#)), Sclerenchyma ([68](#), [113](#)).

Fig. S53. SCLERENCHYMA SCLEREID from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

BLOCKY (BLO)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 5).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 5).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Length varied greatly between 20 and 120 µm.

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were registered during analysis.

BLOCKY appear both in isolated and articulated forms (Fig. S54a-g). Amongst the silica skeletons, two subtypes were identified according to the anatomical origin of the tissue, that is, BLOCKY BULLIFORM and BLOCKY EPIDERMAL (for a discussion, see below).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

BLOCKY was separated from ELONGATE ENTIRE following the criteria defined by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 30). BLOCKY BULLIFORM and BLOCKY EPIDERMAL were separated as the former appears in chains perpendicularly adhered to one of the long sides of elongated phytoliths (Fig. S54f), whereas the latter is often grid-arranged and usually accompanied by hair bases (Fig. S54g).

BLOCKY is produced in several different plant tissues such as leaf bulliforms, epidermal and sub-epidermal cells of grasses and sedges, as well as parenchyma, sclerenchyma and cork from non-herbaceous monocots, dicots, and conifers ([47](#)). Differentiation amongst them is only possible when they appear in anatomical connection. As such, we considered isolated BLOCKY to be a non-diagnostic morphotype, whereas the articulated forms BLOCKY BULLIFORM and BLOCKY EPIDERMAL were classified as diagnostic of Poaceae leaves and Dicotyledonous respectively.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

BLOCKY BULLIFORM: Parallelepipedal bulliform cell ([52](#), [58](#), [59](#), [66](#), [96](#), [101](#)), Bulliform ([97](#)).

BLOCKY EPIDERMAL: Epidermal appendage hair base ([115](#)), Epidermal groundmass polyhedral ([68](#)), Epidermal polygonal ([97](#), [111](#)).

Fig. S54. BLOCKY from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-e) Single-celled BLOCKY. f) Articulated BLOCKY BULLIFORM. g) Articulated BLOCKY EPIDERMAL. Scale bars are 10 µm.

BULLIFORM FLABELLATE (BUL_FL A)

- **Rationale for naming:**

Criteria adopted from ICPN 2.0. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 7).

- **Description (shape, texture and/or ornamentation, symmetrical features):**

See description by Neumann et al. ([47](#) Supplementary Data File 1: 7).

- **Size and morphometrics:**

Longest axis typically 25-60 μm .

- **Subtypes, variants, and articulated forms:**

No subtypes nor variants were registered during analysis. BULLIFORM FLABELLATE was found both isolated and as part of silica skeletons (Fig. S55a-m).

- **Discussion and interpretation:**

BULLIFORM FLABELLATE is known to be formed in the epidermal tissue of Poaceae leaves. Indeed, most authors have classified BULLIFORM FLABELLATE as diagnostic of such tissue ([51](#), [53](#), [56](#), [59](#), [63](#), [64](#), [67](#), [68](#), [91](#), [97](#), [100](#), [111](#), [112](#), [114](#)). A recent study by Chen et al. ([123](#)) on Poaceae from Taiwan showed BULLIFORM FLABELLATE to be very rare within the Pooideae subfamily, as well as the possibility of separating between grass subfamilies depending on the shape of the end profile of BULLIFORM FLABELLATE. As this is one of the first systematic studies on bulliform phytoliths and it has been performed on eastern Asian grasses, we have chosen not to apply that division in our study. Furthermore, a publication by Novello et al. ([62](#)) has shown that Cyperaceae also produces a similar morphotype, and similar results were published for southern American Cyperaceae by Martins and Alves ([124](#)). In fact, ICPN 2.0. considers BULLIFORM FLABELLATE to be present on both Poaceae and Cyperaceae ([47](#)). As a result, we have decided to consider BULLIFORM FLABELLATE as diagnostic of Poaceae/Cyperaceae.

- **Synonyms (ICPN 1.0., discussed authors):**

Fan-shaped ([57](#)), Cuneiform bulliform cell ([51](#), [59](#), [62](#), [64](#), [66](#)), Bulliform ([67](#), [68](#), [97](#), [115](#)).

Fig. S55. BULLIFORM FLABELLATE from archaeological samples from Mezber and Ona Adi. a-k) Single-celled BULLIFORM FLABELLATE. l-m) Articulated BULLIFORM FLABELLATE. Scale bars are 10 μ m.

Dataset S1 (separate file). Results of the morphological and morphometrical analyses of the grinding stones.

Dataset S2 (separate file). Raw data of starch grain analysis.

Dataset S3 (separate file). Raw data of single-celled phytolith analysis.

Dataset S4 (separate file). Raw data of articulated phytolith analysis.

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